

Leibniz Institute of
Ecological Urban and
Regional Development

Book of Abstracts

IOER Conference 2024

Space & Transformation: *Living in Harmony with Nature*

26 to 27 September • Deutsches Hygiene Museum Dresden, Germany

conference.ioer.info

DRESDEN
concept

Book of Abstracts

Published by the
Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER)
on the occasion of the

IOER Conference 2024

"Space & Transformation: Living in Harmony with Nature"

26 to 27 September

Dresden, Germany

conference.ioer.info

#IOERConf

Status: 10.09.2024

Title Image: trealon, pixabay.com

Layout and Artwork: IOER Media

www.ioer.de/en

Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	7
2	Programme Overview.....	8
3	Formats	9
	Presentation	9
	Speed Talk.....	9
	Dialogue Session	9
	Poster Party	9
4	Keynotes	10
	Envisioning positive futures and nature-based solutions for the Anthropocene	11
	Transformative governance: Experimenting, Learning, Changing	12
	Building Ecologically Smart Cities: Mapping human-nature interactions in Bangalore over the centuries.....	13
5	Workshops	14
	“Knowledge Trail, City Nature Dresden Tour”	14
	“Wild Greens Short and Sweet – Take a Nature Walk”	14
	“Biodiversity is life, biodiversity is our life. Let Yoga and Tai Chi connect you to life”	14
	“Joy of Life – Uncovering the Wall Painting by Gerhard Richter at the Hygiene Museum!”	14
6	Tracks.....	15
	Track 1: Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development	16
	Track 2: Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation.....	16
	Track 3: Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations	17
	Track 4: Circularity and resilience in building and settlement development.....	17
	Track 5: Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions	18
	Track 6: Open Topic	18
7	Abstracts.....	19
	Parallel Sessions A	20
	A1 – Rethinking urban wellbeing and mental health from a youth perspective: a participatory mapping exercise in the urban periphery of Sao Paulo.....	21
	A1 – (Un)common grounds for Rights of Nature – philosophical reflections on Living in Harmony with Nature	22
	A1 – Shocking Pop-up Cells of Beauty in the Street – Proposal for +/- Bus-Stop-Size Joint Immersion, Analog and Digital.....	23

A2 – Understanding and using the role of geosocial media data streams in urban social, ecological and technological systems (SETS) for smart governance.....	24
A2 – Governance of Socio-Ecological Systems (SES) Towards Sustainable Transformation in Zambia: A case of the three areas of the Pilot Programme for Climate Resilience (PPCR).....	25
A2 – Transformation Pathways towards a Regenerative Built Environment.....	26
A3 – Prioritizing nature-based solutions to support urban planning: A spatial multi-criteria analysis approach based on ecosystem services.....	27
A3 – Individual vs common greening: A framework for socio-spatial assessment in the social housing buildings in Pune, India.....	28
A3 – Impact of diverse urban green infrastructure types on outdoor thermal comfort in residential neighbourhoods: A microclimatic modelling approach.....	29
A4 – Exploring Synergies and Trade-Offs Between Environmental Risks and Resources for Sustainable Urban Transformation.....	30
A4 – Drivers and barriers of social innovations for a circular built environment: insights from a case study design.....	31
A4 – Flood Damage – Connecting Costs and Material Needs for more sustainable Flood Preparedness.....	32
A5 – Comparative Study of Urban Planning Elements for Carbon Reduction: Public Acceptance in Germany and South Korea.....	33
A5 – Identifying Conservation Gap in Biodiversity Hotspot Areas: Single Flagship Species or Multi-species?.....	34
A5 – Impact Mitigation for highways in the D-A-CH countries – legal basis, effectiveness of implementation and current challenges in the light of climate and landscape change.....	35
A6 – Expression vs. Continuation. On a Necessary Transformation in the Epistemology and Methodology of Architectural Design.....	36
A6 – Architecture of Subtraction: An Investigation on the Potential of the Concept of Subtraction in Transforming the Discipline of Architecture.....	37
A6 – Every-pair interactions and their applications in spatial problems.....	38
Parallel Sessions B.....	39
B1 – Space-related sufficiency strategies: Building blocks for transformation?.....	40
B2 – How to deal with the complexity of transformation processes in policy consulting: An exchange of experiences and methods.....	42
B3 – Spatial tools to model a global transformation towards a bio-based built environment.....	43
B3 – From Traffic Data to Traffic Insights: A Case Study in Dresden.....	44
B4 – Crafting Urban Resilience and Circular Economy: Insights from Open Labs in the FabCity Initiative Hamburg.....	45
B4 – Negotiating Biophysical Limits of the Bioeconomy in EU Policy.....	46
B5 – A long-term ecological perspective and its integration with local knowledge is a requisite for sustainable regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity.....	47
B5 – Assessing the Drought and Heat Risks for Urban Green Infrastructure: Case of Plauen, Germany.....	48
B5 – Land Transitions and Socio-Ecological Restructuring at the Urban-rural Interface: A Case Study of Huangyan/Taizhou in China.....	49
B6 – Imaginaries of inside-out place making: sensing, designing and transforming (urban) spaces with humans and the non-human world for sustainable and climate resilient futures.....	50

Parallel Sessions C.....	52
C1 – Discursive greening: local political debates in urban greening and biodiversity planning and implementation in German and Italian municipalities	53
C1 – Pond of liquid bodies. A resonance artificial landscape through acoustic agreements and vibrant evidences, based on imagist poems.....	54
C1 – Planning the urban greening: is it a standardised necessity or a necessary evil, the case of Samsun.....	55
C2 – Speaking as proxy for Nature: A multispecies role-play on conflicts in urban energy transitions.....	56
C3 – The IOER Research Data Centre – data, simulations and tools for the sustainable transformation of neighbourhoods, cities, and regions.....	57
C3 – Semantic data model for municipal landscape planning in Germany: An approach for modelling landscape planning content in data standards.....	58
C3 – Influences of land use structure on well-being within the context of urban areas.....	59
C4 – Assessing use of urban green spaces to inform planning for biodiversity and equitable access.....	60
C4 – Do fragile urban systems intensify urban vulnerability? An inquiry into the case of Mongla port municipality of Bagerhat district of Bangladesh.....	61
C4 – An Urban Rivers Renaissance? Stream restoration and Green-Blue Infrastructure in Latin America – Insights from urban planning in Colombia.....	62
C6 – Shifting the Paradigm: Situating South-North climate adaptation research collaborations in the intersection of equity and decolonisation.....	63
Parallel Sessions D	65
D1 – Urban human-nature partnership – a positive vision for planning post-anthropocentric cities.....	66
D1 – Dimensions and practices of cultural-spiritual human-nature (re)connection in Chennai, India.....	67
D1 – Building Environmental and Community Resilience through Active Citizenship: From Theory to Practice.....	68
D2 – Factors promoting the creation and development of regional parks and green belts – a policy process perspective.....	69
D2 – Ecological glimpses. Or how architectural education encompasses environmental matters.....	70
D2 – Trajectories of mining ecosystems in the perspective of human-environment interrelations.....	71
D3 – Indikatoren zu Ökosystemen und ihren Leistungen für Deutschland im neuen IÖR-Forschungsdatenzentrum.....	72
D3 – Different policies and different urban form? Policy impacts on the urban form in the French-German border-region.....	73
D3 – Understand the evolving human-river relationships with social science methods.....	74
D4 – Leveraging transformative change for biodiversity in spatial planning: Science meets practice.....	75
D5 – Conflicts as indicators of socio-ecological injustices in urban energy transitions.....	76
D5 – How can effectiveness be balanced with cost in biodiversity conservation? Cross-scale ecological network planning in the Yangtze River Delta, China.....	77
D5 – New Insights into intercity ecological synergy: revealing community structures and their drivers through the dynamics of ecosystem service flows.....	78

Parallel Sessions E.....	79
E1 – Nature's diverse values in urban planning: uncovering conflicting and shared views from the inner worlds of planners.....	80
E1 – Piloting the fosterage of urban residents' resonances with nature through a 5-week-long ritual: Learnings, limits and lookout for sustainability transformations.....	81
E1 – Using Human Scale Development Approach for Transformative Visions in Spatial Development.....	82
E2 – An Art-Based Research Workshop on Envisioning Co-Existence of Wolves and People in Fragmented Landscapes.....	83
E3 – A Digital Tool for Green Infrastructure Planning in Metropolitan Rural Areas for Multi-Scenario Needs.....	84
E3 – Atmosphären und leibliche Kommunikation als Dimensionen lebenswerter und nachhaltiger Wohngebiete.....	85
E3 – A new beginning for Strasbourg's green belt.....	87
E5 – An IPBES-like assessment for Germany's urban areas: Insights from the project "Faktencheck Artenvielfalt".....	88
E5 – Perspectives of landscape criticality.....	89
E5 – A conceptual framework to study transformative change and innovation in non-core regions and steps towards operationalisation.....	90
Poster Party.....	91
Inspiring Positive Visions of a Sustainable Future with Solar Cookers.....	92
KlimaOasen – A participatory process to develop nature-based solutions on the University of Stuttgart's campuses.....	93
Investigating the Effects of Green Walls on Local Climate Regulation: A Case Study for Dresden.....	94
Transformation Pathways towards a Regenerative Built Environment.....	95
Compensation planning and implementation for infrastructure projects against the background of increasing drought and water shortage.....	96
A study on Urban-Scale Aerodynamic Roughness Length and Sky View Factor Analysis Using Airborne LiDAR Remote Sensing.....	97
LSUTDI: A Hybrid Deep Learning Model for Imputing Large-Scale Urban Traffic Data.....	98
SALUTE4CE Integrated environmental management of small green spaces in urban areas.....	99
Social and innovative Platform On cultural Tourism (SPOT) and its potential towards deepening Europeanisation.....	99
Do the nesting holes suit the bee? Validating expert estimation of wild bee habitat with findings from field studies.....	99
Open space, policy, planning, chance.....	99
University Campus Healthscapes: Using the university as an urban lab for designing health-promoting built-environments.....	100
8 Venue floor plan & directions.....	101
Deutsches Hygiene Museum Dresden Orientation Plan.....	101
Map and directions to the <i>Zentrum für Baukultur (ZfBK)</i> in the <i>Kulturpalast</i>	102
9 Acknowledgements.....	103

1 Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated in drastic fashion the inextricable link between human well-being and healthy ecosystems. Today, however, ecosystems and biodiversity around the world are facing considerable societal pressures and are moving dangerously close to critical tipping points: ecosystems and their services are being degraded to such an extent that more than one million animal and plant species are threatened with extinction. Significant non-renewable natural resources are being overexploited while cascading environmental risks threaten the livelihoods of large sections of the population. For these reasons, transformative change seems more urgent than ever.

This is particularly true with regard to spatial development, insofar as the relationship between humans and nature is negotiated and shaped directly in landscapes, regions, cities and urban districts. So what needs to be achieved in spatial development within the next 10 to 20 years to ensure that humans can permanently live in harmony with nature? How can novel human-nature partnerships and vibrant human-nature relationships be shaped at different spatial scales?

These questions are at the heart of the IOER Conference 2024. In the run-up to the UN Summit of the Future 2024, we investigate which spatial approaches and methods can help to greatly accelerate the replacement of destructive ways of living and doing business with sustainable ones. In particular, the focus is on perspectives and approaches that can enable and drive such transformative change, such as:

- Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development;
- Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalization;
- Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations;
- Circularity and resilience in building and settlement development;
- Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions.

At the [IOER Conference 2024](#), we wish to address the urgent need for social, ecological and technical systems, targets and transformation knowledge on spatial development. You can look forward to presentations by German and international experts and actors as well as by scientists from all IOER research areas. As part of the conference, the Dresden Leibniz Graduate School, jointly run by the IOER and TU Dresden, is organizing its international [Summer School](#) for PhD students on the same overarching topic on 25 September 2024.

2 Programme Overview

Thursday, 26th September

08:00	Registration
	Musical Intervention
09:00–10:30	Opening Remarks Keynote Group Photo
10:30–11:00	<i>Break</i>
11:00–12:30	Parallel Sessions A
12:30–13:30	Lunch Break Self-Guided Photo Exhibition
13:30–14:40	Keynote Musical Intervention
14:40–14:45	<i>Room Shift</i>
14:45–16:15	Parallel Sessions B
16:15–16:45	<i>Break</i>
16:45–18:15	Parallel Sessions C
18:15	Workshops
From 19:00	Poster Party at ZfBK

Friday, 27th September

09:00	Opening Remarks
09:00–10:45	Virtual Keynote & Panel Discussion Musical Intervention
10:45–11:15	<i>Break</i>
11:15–12:45	Parallel Sessions D
12:45	Lunch Break Self-Guided Photo Exhibition Musical Intervention
13:35–13:45	<i>Room Shift</i>
13:45–15:15	Parallel Sessions E
15:15–15:30	<i>Room Shift</i>
15:30	Closing Statements
	Farewell Networking (Post Card Activity)

Visit the IOER conference website to access the full programme:

<https://conference.ioer.info/en/programme>

3 Formats

Presentation

Papers intended for publication in a scientific journal can be explained in a detailed presentation of 20 minutes. In addition to the contributions from several speakers this format allows for in-depth discussions with the audience.

All accepted papers will be evaluated with regard to their suitability for publication in peer-reviewed journals and grouped according to research topic. For these contributions, the conference team will work with the session organizers to develop options for joint publication (e.g. Special Issue, Thematic Collection).

Speed Talk

New project ideas, research approaches or other impulses can be presented very concisely in a short presentation of 9 minutes. The emphasis of this format is on engaging the audience, mutual inspiration and joint discussions.

Dialogue Session

Sessions of 60 minutes duration can be proposed in which the focus is entirely on communication and interaction. The content and methodology of these sessions can be freely chosen by the proposing session organizer and must be described in the submission. Priority will be given to highly co-creative formats – standard presentations will not be accepted here. Dialogue sessions are also suitable for the involvement of practitioners and may therefore be held in German, if desired. A laptop is available in dialogue session rooms as well as a projector and screen, a pin board, moderation materials and seating.

Poster Party

Accepted scientific posters will be exhibited at the Centre for Building Culture Saxony (Zentrum für Baukultur Sachsen/ZfBK) in Dresden's Kulturpalast (downtown) for the entire duration of the IOER conference from 26–27 September. A list of poster submissions can be found here in the book of abstracts. Posters should be size DIN A0 (portrait). Please send your poster to dtp@ioer.de with the subject line "IOER Conference 2024" by September 15, 2024 – we will print the poster for you!

At a poster party on the evening of 26 September participants will have a chance to give a short presentation, view the other posters and network with attendees. There will also be music, catering and drinks.

4 Keynotes

Our esteemed keynote speakers

We have the honour of welcoming three esteemed keynote speakers – Prof. Nancy B. Grimm, Prof. James Evans, and Prof. Harini Nagendra – who will share their invaluable insights on nature-based solutions, transformative governance, and building ecologically smart cities. Their extensive expertise and pioneering work in these fields will undoubtedly contribute to fruitful and constructive discussions on how we can live in harmony with nature and create sustainable urban environments.

Keynote Speaker

Prof. Nancy B. Grimm

Photo: private

She is a Regents Professor at Arizona State University, is an ecosystem ecologist who studies the interactions of climate change, human activities, resilience, and biogeochemical processes in urban and stream ecosystems. Grimm was founding director of the Central Arizona–Phoenix LTER, co-directed the Urban Resilience to Extremes Sustainability Research Network, and now co-directs the NATURA and ESSA networks, all focused on solving problems of the Anthropocene, especially in cities. Her research centers on nature-based, technological, and governance solutions that can build resilience to a future with increased frequency and magnitude of extreme events. In streams, Grimm studies how hydrologic and climatic variability, and more recently, wildfire, influence ecosystem processes such as stream metabolism and nutrient dynamics. Grimm was President of the Ecological Society of America and is a Fellow of the American Association for the Advancement of Science, the American Geophysical Union, the Ecological Society of America, the Society for Freshwater Science. She is a member of the United States National Academy of Sciences and has made >230 contributions to the scientific literature with colleagues and students.

Keynote Title

Envisioning positive futures and nature-based solutions for the Anthropocene

The Anthropocene, an age where humans have become the main force shaping the environment, is characterized by rapid change, compounded problems, and increasing complexity and uncertainty. For cities, extreme events driven by climate change pose particular challenges, including threats to lives and livelihoods, compounded infrastructure failures, and unequal distribution of risk due to past unjust practices. Strengthening the capacity of these social-ecological-technological systems (SETS) to maintain their essential structure and function when faced with such events (i.e., resilience) is of paramount importance. Yet solutions have been based on prevailing views that the world is complicated, not complex; that events are predictable, not uncertain; and that people are apart from nature rather than part of nature. In this talk I will explore examples of nature-based solutions, asking if these strategies can build resilience to extreme events in cities. Co-produced visions for present and future urban configurations from neighborhood to regional scales will illustrate the potential for reducing risk from extreme heat and flooding in urbanized central Arizona.

Prof. Grimm's Arizona State University profile page:

<https://search.asu.edu/profile/71704>

Keynote Speaker

Prof. James Evans

Photo: private

He currently directs the Manchester Urban Institute at the University of Manchester, where previously he was Head of the Geography Department. He researches how cities learn to become smarter and more sustainable, and his work on urban living labs and mobile methods has been foundational across the social sciences. He is passionate about the role of universities in delivering urban sustainability, working with hundreds of organisations around the world. He has led numerous applied interdisciplinary projects on this topic, helping to generate more than £60 million of research and innovation funding and more than 100 publications. He is Field Chief Editor for the journal *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities* and CEO of a university spin out Urban 360 Ltd.

Keynote Title

Transformative governance: Experimenting, Learning, Changing

How can we reduce inequalities and enable communities to flourish in a sustainable way? How do we scale innovations like active travel to improve population health and sustainability at regional and national levels? How can we mainstream cross-sectoral approaches that are able to address challenges like poor health, climate change and low productivity holistically?

This presentation presents a range of experiences with new forms of governance that have attempted to address these challenges over the past twenty years. It begins by considering the phenomenon of urban experimentation and the growing emphasis on demonstration and pilot projects to trial sustainable forms of development. Even when successful though, pilots often fail to scale up and drive the wider transformation of places.

The lecture argues that the wider transformation of places requires a wider transformation of organisations. Specifically, organisations need to be able to both learn from experiments and trials and change how they operate. Taking learning seriously sheds light on why place-based innovation requires different kinds of thinking and practices to mainstream economic and policy innovation. The presentation concludes by considering the implications for sustainable transformation more broadly.

Prof. Evans' University of Manchester profile page:

<https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/persons/james.z.evans>

Keynote Speaker

Prof. Harini Nagendra

Photo: Ankit Kumar Mangal

She is the Director of the Centre for Climate Change and Sustainability at Azim Premji University. She is known for her research spanning over 30 years on forest conservation and urban sustainability, with several seminal publications and awards including the 2009 Cozzarelli Prize from the US National Academy of Sciences and the 2013 Elinor Ostrom Senior Scholar award. She is an elected member of The World Academy of Sciences and the Indian National Science Academy. She has written a number of award-winning non-fiction books including, most recently, *Shades of Blue: Connecting the Drops in India's Cities*. She also writes the acclaimed Bangalore Detectives Club historical mystery series, set in 1920s colonial Bangalore. Prof. Nagendra serves on the Advisory Board of the European Institute of Innovation and Technology's Climate-KIC and the WRI Ross Centre for Sustainable Cities, and is co-editor-in-chief of the journal *Global Environmental Change*.

Keynote Title

Building Ecologically Smart Cities: Mapping human-nature interactions in Bangalore over the centuries

Cities are on a breakneck path to growth, especially in the global South. It has never been more clear why we must begin to think ecologically about our urban future. Drawing on the deep ecological history of Bangalore – one of India's largest and fastest growing cities – I will discuss how some of the earliest residents of this semi-arid landscape relied on a three-dimensional spatial imagination of interconnected settlements. While many of these ideas were lost as the city grew and began to rely on water and food imported from increasing distances, in recent years the exposure of the city to heat and drought has made communities revisit many of these ideas. This presentation will also highlight the use of an interdisciplinary suite of approaches including GIS, remote sensing and the use of historical maps linked with oral histories, ecological analyses and social interviews to increase our spatial and temporal understanding, helping to visualize how we can re-design ecologically smart cities, to accommodate both nature and human wellbeing.

Prof. Nagendra's Azim Premji University profile page:

<https://azimpremjiuniversity.edu.in/people/harini-nagendra>

5 Workshops

“Knowledge Trail, City Nature Dresden Tour”

Photo: H. Hensel/IOER-Media

Explore an educational trail together with two of our senior scientists (supported by digital & in-person signage). Find out interesting facts concerning the services of various ecosystems from natural areas in Dresden.

Speakers: Henriette John & Ralf-Uwe Syrbe

“Wild Greens Short and Sweet – Take a Nature Walk”

Photo: A. Schielicke/IOER-Media

Take a wander in the Großer Garten of Dresden with a local guide to learn more about the edible plants located there.

Speaker: Tom Zschaage

“Biodiversity is life, biodiversity is our life. Let Yoga and Tai Chi connect you to life”

Photo: Lina Trochez on unsplash

After a fruitful day of networking and discussion we invite you to explore your inner world. Recharge your batteries with practices of Tai Chi and Yoga and feel your intuitive connection to nature and whole life. You don't need to bring any equipment for the workshop, only take care to wear flat shoes. The workshop will be outside in the park area close to the conference venue. In case of rain, the workshop will be conducted inside.

Speakers: Sophie Meier & Suili Xiao

“Joy of Life – Uncovering the Wall Painting by Gerhard Richter at the Hygiene Museum!”

Photo: Andreas Rost; DHMD

Marvel at the 60 square meter painting together with staff from the Hygiene Museum created by the famous artist Gerhard Richter. Don't miss this rare occasion to view a painting that until recently was hidden behind white paint.

Speaker: Deutsches Hygiene-Museum Dresden

6 Tracks

Based on the conference's theme "Space & Transformation: Living in Harmony with Nature" and the research scope of the IOER the conference sessions were divided into thematic tracks so that the various foci could be easily identified.

Photo: Neil Thomas on unsplash.com

Track 1: Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

Global urbanisation is a particular cause of the increasing alienation of humans from non-human nature, along with technologization and digitalisation. Discourses within political debates as well as the media and environmental protection movements paint dystopian futures that will result from dwindling relationships between humans and nature where climate change and the mass extinction of animals, plants and ecosystems go hand in hand with the extinction of humankind. The question here is: How can we create positive urban and regional visions that enable us to understand the urgently required shift towards sustainability not as some kind of renunciation or a restriction in freedom but as one essential aspect of a good life? Which discourses allow us to view nature as an equal partner so that we respect her limits? Which leverage points and actors need to be addressed in order to integrate resonant human-nature relationships into our everyday actions? What role is played by inner shifts and changes in our values, beliefs and worldviews that currently divide us from nature?

Track 2: Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

Nature is an indispensable factor to be considered if we wish cities and regions to continue to be liveable and just places in the future. It is equally crucial to adapt to climate change, to promote climate-neutral living, to enable contact with and experience of nature and ultimately to offer public open spaces that are inclusive and foster a sense of community. Yet there are various challenges to the regeneration, preservation and promotion of nature, particularly in existing urban areas: Transformative policy, planning and management approaches are needed to resolve tensions between competing forms of land use as well as ownership and land availability, to fill funding gaps and to reconcile divergent options for utilisation. How can urban nature be enhanced in the revitalization of existing urban fabrics and building stock despite demands for re-densification and while observing laws to protect the built heritage and resolving conflicts of use? How can urban nature become part of a wide-ranging understanding of our civic (built) culture? What role do nature conservation and environmental protection play in promoting as well as restricting usable urban nature? Which governance models are needed to ensure and realise permanent and binding shared responsibility for urban nature between the public and private sector as well as civil society?

Track 3: Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

Transformation towards sustainability is closely linked to spatial structures and processes that require tools for informed decision-making such as spatial indicators, analyses, models, simulations and other techniques. Among other things, there is a need to overcome the challenge of competing forms of land use while recognising the role of property and striving to preserve the biosphere. How can diverging interests in land use and spatial structures be reconciled and what solutions are available for aligning a sustainable development of e.g. settlements, energy and food systems? How can data-driven and data-based approaches help to provide the required systems-, target- and transformation knowledge? How can they ensure to match stakeholders' information needs and interaction forms to support collective decision making for transformative change? What are crucial gaps in data or methods to address complex interactions, goal conflicts and trade-offs regarding e.g. climate neutrality, biodiversity, circularity and resilience?

Track 4: Circularity and resilience in building and settlement development

In view of the grand challenges that the social-ecological crisis implies for a sustainable building and settlement development the concepts of circularity and resilience have received growing attention and may offer effective responses. On the one hand, circularity is rooted in the use of existing anthropogenic materials while minimising the consumption of natural resources. On the other hand, resilience strategies and measures, are intended to address challenges such as climate change and to strengthen the robustness of places in the face of natural disasters and social challenges. What approaches are suited to assess and implement these two concepts respectively in spatial development practice? And how can circularity and resilience be achieved simultaneously? Which conflicts and synergies may arise due to the different objectives of the two concepts– for nature and with nature? What methods and concepts can help to mitigate such conflicts and strengthen synergies?

Track 5: Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

Around the world, landscapes, ecosystems and biodiversity are under pressure due to the spatial utilisation of land. Landscapes are facing fundamental changes as renewable energy sectors undergo expansion. Ecosystems and their services are becoming degraded. Globally, however, the burden of destruction is unevenly distributed: The Global South is disproportionately affected by the impact of climate change, especially considering its lower share of emissions compared to other regions in the world. More than one million animal and plant species are threatened with extinction. The COVID-19 pandemic provided a drastic and salutary lesson on how closely interwoven a healthy life is with healthy ecosystems. So what needs to be done to once again live in harmony with nature and recognise that our resource-intensive lifestyles and economies are not only destroying ecosystems and species but also our own livelihoods? What do balanced landscape scenarios look like? How can ecosystems be restored and protected in line with Targets 2 and 3 of the UN Convention on Biological Diversity? How can we achieve a biodiversity net gain, i.e. an expansion (Nature Positive) in habitats for biological diversity in order to reverse the trend of species extinction? And how can especially nature-based solutions help in this?

Track 6: Open Topic

Contributions aligned with the basic theme of the conference, but which cannot be assigned to one of the specific topics can be submitted here.

7 Abstracts

The following section presents the conference abstracts, sorted in chronological order by session. The format and associated track are named as well.

Abstracts

Parallel Sessions A

Parallel Session: A1
Format: Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

A1 – Rethinking urban wellbeing and mental health from a youth perspective: a participatory mapping exercise in the urban periphery of Sao Paulo

Interconnected challenges, such as the persistent impacts of the covid-19 pandemic, the climate emergency and the increasing precariousness of education and employment, as well as the destruction of nature in rapidly urbanizing areas, have significantly influenced how young people and young adults make sense of their daily lives, imagine their future, and adapt to well-being concerns (Börner 2023). In 2020, the UN warned that mental health should be at the centre of discussions on post-pandemic recovery. As a mental health pandemic is on the rise, public policies and interventions continue to inadequately address the immediate and long-term wellbeing needs of marginalised youth, particularly in the urban peripheries of the global South that suffer from both acute and chronic disaster risk (Börner 2023; Börner et al. forthcoming). At the same time, there is a need to de- and re-construct Western binary concepts of 'mental-physical' wellbeing and inner-outer sustainability transformations (Woiwode et al. 2021), based on alternative conceptualisations of 'mental' wellbeing and human-nature relations (Mueller et al. 2023; Kim et al. 2023). This contribution explores the lessons learned from a participatory photo-voice (Koeckler et al. 2024) and body-territory mapping workshop (Gorrell Barnes et al. 2024; Zaragocin et al. 2021) that will be conducted in August 2024 with students from the University of Sao Paulo in the Eastern urban periphery of the city. The aim is to develop alternative psychosocial conceptualisations of urban wellbeing that change the ways we experience and relate to self, others, as well as everything around us (Núñez, 2019; Börner et al., forthcoming).

Authors

Susanne Boerner University of Birmingham

Parallel Session: A1
Format: Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

A1 – (Un)common grounds for Rights of Nature – philosophical reflections on Living in Harmony with Nature

The Rights of Nature (RoN) are the fastest-growing legal movement of our times. Numerous countries globally have granted subjective legal rights to various natural entities, including rivers, mountains, glaciers, and lagoons, as well as to nature as a whole. I explore the philosophical question of whether a common ground can, should, and does exist for these diverse legal initiatives. I examine different approaches, including holistic narratives and imaginaries (Anthropocene, Blue Marble, common heritage), international and national political agreements (Paris Agreement, Constitution of Ecuador, Treaty of Waitangi in New Zealand), and philosophical frameworks (land ethic, earth jurisprudence, earth law, Earth System Thinking). I acknowledge the complexity of establishing a common ground, given that it can encompass both: a shared geographic territory (spatial dimension) and a shared understanding (semantic dimension). Despite some overlapping justifications for RoN, such as the attribution of non-instrumental value to the natural environment, there are significant controversies, particularly regarding the spatial dimension. Issues like affectedness by and responsibility for ecological damages vary based on geo-political and socio-economic factors. Additionally, most RoN codifications focus on singular natural entities with specific local challenges, conflicts, and cultural traditions, making a universal approach more challenging. Nonetheless, the "magic of rights" lies in their ability to serve as a formal yet flexible governance tool, translating diverse local beliefs and demands.

Authors

Stefan Knauß MLU Halle-Wittenberg / UFZ / iDiv

Parallel Session: A1
Format: Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

A1 – Shocking Pop-up Cells of Beauty in the Street – Proposal for +/- Bus-Stop-Size Joint Immersion, Analog and Digital

1. Externalization of Wisdom and the Imperative of Immersion

Since the rise of oral cultures, various media revolutions externalized knowledge and, by extent, objectivity. The advent of digital media suggests the imperative of immersion, and, therefore, subjectivity. Can we augment Immanuel Kant's educational "sa-pere aude!" through the contemporary entertainment imperative of "entertain me"?

2. Nudging towards Stunning Beauty

Let's divert Thaler's and Sunstein's nudge concept to punctuate the mediocrity of the contemporary city with beautiful everyday surprises. How about the pop-up design of tiny, essential, maybe ultimate landscape-/architectural beauty displayed on the streets to substantiate how environment can, and should, be? Suddenly, the "inhospitality" of the modern city (Alexander Mitscherlich) would transform into an involuntarily, and unavoidable, mental map of authentic, immersive, and subversive experiments in the city.

3. Cut-Continuance and Metaphorical Design

Can we pair the aesthetic cut-continuance "Kire" (Ryōsuke Ōhashi) with the "Aesthetics of the Japanese Lunchbox" (Kenji Ekuan)? "Kire" unites the beauty of art and the beauty of nature in, and as, a work of art. The quadripartite structure of the Japanese lunchbox allows us to design metaphorically, to expedite Augmented Reality and, consequently, serve educational as well as community purposes.

4. Discussion: Beauty Spots and Urban Paradigm Shift

Modern urban design worked top-down, from an aerial view. Let's start to design bottom-up with "The art of looking sideways" (Alan Fletcher) and "the good Lord ... in the detail" (Aby Warburg). Contemporary glitch art, guerilla design and subvertising demonstrate how immediate impact allows for immediate stand-alone quality. Does exemplary beauty create hope for new environmental design paradigms, and well as a bad conscience for unkind urban planning?

Authors

Niels-Christian Fritsche Technische Universität Dresden

Parallel Session: A2
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools of transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalization

A2 – Understanding and using the role of geosocial media data streams in urban social, ecological and technological systems (SETS) for smart governance.

The SETS framework provides a basis for making sense of complex intertwined components in today's ecosystems, bridging social, ecological and technological factors. One largely ignored component is algorithms and the global spread of information through geosocial media data streams. These data streams are systematically and significantly influencing and changing the behavior of many people, with widespread consequences on the environment. This requires analysts to first map the status quo of geosocial media patterns for use in decision making. Research has shown great potential for harnessing these sources for societal benefit, from crowdsensing approaches in social geography, to participatory use cases in landscape and urban planning, to specific applications (e.g. monitoring human-environment interactions in disaster management, pandemic spread analysis, traffic monitoring, smart cities). In practice, however, user privacy and data accessibility are persistent barriers that limit data use. As a result, socially useful data collections remain disconnected silos. Our proposed analytical framework specifically addresses these practical challenges in geosocial data dissemination, while integrating the analysis under the conceptual umbrella of the SETS framework. In particular, our contribution helps to systematically identify many currently untapped opportunities and integrate robust data-based solutions into smart governance. The overall focus of this work is to integrate geosocial data streams into urban decision making and to harness their potential to guide sustainable change. The SETS framework is used as an umbrella to explain the interdependencies between components and to identify levers for action.

Authors

Alexander Dunkel Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: A2
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools of transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalization

A2 – Governance of Socio-Ecological Systems (SES) Towards Sustainable Transformation in Zambia: A case of the three areas of the Pilot Programme for Climate Resilience (PPCR)

The governance of Socio-Ecological Systems (SES) in Zambia is not done in a sustainable transformative manner. Thus, the research intends to establish why there is no transformative governance of SES in Zambia and how it can be achieved.

A case study approach will be used from the three areas of the Pilot Programme for Climate Resilience (PPCR) in Zambia namely Transforming Landscapes for Resilience and Development (TRALARD), Strengthening Climate Resilience in Kafue Sub-Basin (SCRiKA) and Strengthening Climate Resilience in Barotse Sub-Basin (SCReBS). These World Bank and African Development Bank funded projects focus on improving natural resource management and interventions to improve the adaptive capacity of vulnerable communities to climate change that affects livelihoods. In addition, other projects' governance framework of SES that are within geographical areas of the three PPCR will be analysed. Lastly, two control points will be used namely Zambia Integrated Forest Landscape Project (ZIFLP) and Ecosystem Conservation and Community Livelihood Enhancement in North Western Zambia.

The research will be theoretical, a document analysis or assessment of institutional structures and legal framework among the PPCR projects on how transformative governance is incorporated in the management of SES. The variables that would be used for analysis are structures, laws, capacity, standards, information flows, paradigms, norms, beliefs and values. The variables will be analysed in the project's Implementation Manuals, Project Appraisal Documents and the legal documents of Zambia

The expected findings are that the PPCR is trying to address the shallow leverage points instead of the deep leverage points (structures, laws, capacity, standards, information flows, paradigms, norms, beliefs and values) to attain sustainable transformative governance of SES.

The conclusion that would be reached is that, the governance system should focus on deep leverage points so as to have transformative change that leads to sustainable transformative governance of SES in Zambia.

Authors

Nathan Namatama Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development / Technische Universität Dresden

Wolfgang Wende Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development / Technische Universität Dresden

Regine Ortlepp Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: A2
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools of transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalization

A2 – Transformation Pathways towards a Regenerative Built Environment

In recent decades, the frequency and intensity of extreme climate events have increased as a consequence of accelerated global warming. High levels of greenhouse gas emissions in the air are threatening fragile ecosystems and vulnerable communities. A significant source of carbon emissions will continue to be global building stocks, which are expected to double by 2050. Therefore, cities, understood as socio-ecological nodes, are a central lever to address the mega-trend of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions growth.

Projections for 2100 indicate the need for a paradigm shift in development and climate change mitigation strategies, including moving beyond mere net-zero targets and actively work towards achieving negative carbon emission balances. In this context, we see the need to move past the 'sustainability' idea towards 'regenerative development', which integrates the internal and external dimensions of the socio-ecological system with the aim to unlearn extractive practices and re-connect human activity with the Earth's natural systems.

This paper analyses how the idea of a regenerative built environment has been implemented in four different contexts reflecting the particular conditions of the Global South and North. We present the multi-faceted learnings of Transformation Labs addressing the construction sectors in Berlin-Brandenburg (Germany), Cape Town Region (South Africa), Bali-Denpasar (Indonesia), and Thimphu-Paro (Bhutan). Central is the holistic focus on material transitions in construction towards nature-based supply chains, including its socio-spatial, environmental, and political dimensions. First results show that several factors are challenging for a regenerative built environment. Among them are the missing market for reclaimed materials, the novelty of working with renewable materials, the acceptance of such approaches in society, and the extended role of architects. In summary, there is a long way to go for regenerative practices in construction to become acknowledged and widely used while first prototypes are perceived as beautiful, sustainable, and achieved through innovative collaborations.

Authors

Georg Hubmann Bauhaus der Erde gGmbH

Parallel Session: A3
Format: Presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

A3 – Prioritizing nature-based solutions to support urban planning: A spatial multi-criteria analysis approach based on ecosystem services

The implementation of nature-based solutions (NBS) is crucial for promoting the sustainability and resilience of cities through enhancing urban ecosystem services (ES) to address societal challenges. While studies aimed at integrating ES assessments into urban planning have increased recently, translating ES assessments into practical recommendations for NBS implementation remains rare and challenging. This study presents a comprehensive framework for the spatial prioritization of NBS to support urban planning at 5 m resolution, leveraging an ES-based multi-criteria analysis approach. We used InVEST to map and assess four ES (habitat quality, urban cooling, urban flood risk mitigation, and urban nature-based recreation) in Stockholm, Sweden, harnessing the novel biotope database BIOTOP SE. We identified hotspots of the ES and synergies and trade-offs both globally and locally between the ES. The priority maps of three NBS (installing green roofs, de-sealing parking lots, and developing pocket parks) were derived using ES-based criteria and other associated criteria to create the building-scale spatially explicit recommendations on locations for NBS implementation. By prioritizing NBS in areas with less ES provision, this approach not only advances spatial justice but also contributes to the enhancement of climate resilience within urban contexts. This study offers a practical approach for urban planners and policymakers seeking to integrate ecosystem services into the fabric of spatial development, paving the way for more sustainable, resilient, and equitable urban futures.

Authors

Jiayu Zheng TU Dortmund

Parallel Session: A3
Format: Presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

A3 – Individual vs common greening: A framework for socio-spatial assessment in the social housing buildings in Pune, India

In the context of rapid urbanisation, new green spaces within the built environment are seen as an approach to combat two challenges: regenerate green cover to support biodiversity and create shared spaces of refuge and leisure for people. In India, a lack of participatory approaches and incentives leads to inadequate communal green spaces. This situation is particularly evident in social housing buildings, where inhabitants must deal with urban greening themselves, even with limited resources and authority. Understanding such bottom-up greening approaches can offer valuable insights into the needs and habits of the inhabitants and present the need for a systematic assessment that can guide the implementation of ad hoc policy instruments for participatory spatial design. Thus, the research question is the following – How to assess individual and common greening approaches in the context of social housing in India?

Using a socio-spatial lens, the research focuses on an empirical case of a social housing project in the city of Pune, India. We propose an assessment framework that, through social, environmental, economic and spatial indicators, seeks to understand the spatial opportunities and barriers for the bottom-up production of green spaces according to the social needs of the inhabitants. The data from architectural drawings, ethnographic surveys, interviews and field observations will be coherently assessed. The initial findings highlight the advantages as well as limitations of greening due to the material qualities of building form; for example, the cantilever balconies influence positively the private green refuge, while the concrete construction hinders the ground-level plantation of large trees for social gatherings.

This research contributes to the debates on urban greening with a new perspective from the cities of eastern countries, rising scholarship in urban studies towards socio-spatial methodological approaches, and useful guidelines to revisit the architectural and spatial planning regulations in the local context.

Authors

Aboli Mangire HafenCity University Hamburg

Alessandro Arlati HafenCity University Hamburg

Parallel Session: A3
Format: Presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

A3 – Impact of diverse urban green infrastructure types on outdoor thermal comfort in residential neighbourhoods: A microclimatic modelling approach

Urbanization has made heat stress an urgent concern in cities, especially in the humid subtropical regions. Consequently, climate conscious design of outdoor spaces is imperative for user wellbeing and livable urban areas. A well acknowledged measure to alleviate heat in outdoor spaces is urban green infrastructure (UGI). However, the individual and combined cooling impact of diverse UGI types, like trees, green walls, and green roofs, is under explored, particularly in realistic urban settings with distinct built morphologies. This study, therefore, explores two typical residential typologies in Dehradun, India, with distinct tree canopy cover, sky view factor, building orientation, height and layout. Scenario modelling with 3D simulation software, ENVI-met, is employed to assess the cooling impact of UGI. Moreover, metrics like physiological equivalent temperature (PET), outdoor thermal comfort autonomy (OTCA) are used to analyse spatial and temporal variability in the cooling impact of the UGI types. The research findings indicate that trees have better cooling potential (upto avg. 9°C PET) which is further enhanced by strategic UGI planning using optimum tree species and planting arrangement. Conversely, building greening does not show substantial pedestrian thermal comfort irrespective of the differences in built morphology. Green walls exhibit slightly better performance than green roofs but are still inconsequential for heat mitigation. Slight impact of building height and wind direction became evident in cooling impact of extensive green roofs. Overall, the influence of built morphology was visible on heat stress on the sites but not on the cooling performance of the different UGI types. In conclusion, this study provides extensive empirical evidence for climate conscious design of outdoor spaces in similar urban and climatic contexts.

Authors

Sana Javaid Technical University of Munich / Dresden Leibniz Graduate School

Wolfgang Wende Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development / Technische Universität Dresden

Stephan Pauleit Technical University of Munich

Parallel Session: A4
Format: Presentation
Track: 4. Circularity and resilience in building and settlement development

A4 – Exploring Synergies and Trade-Offs Between Environmental Risks and Resources for Sustainable Urban Transformation

The pursuit for sustainable urban transformation requires a comprehensive examination of the intricate interchange between environmental risks and resources arising due to climate change and urbanization impacts. In this regard, the study attempts to explore the synergies and trade-offs between environmental risks and resource utilization to identify the key leverages for sustainable transformation using scoping literature review. First key criteria are designed to include to the environmental risks of flooding, drought, earthquake and heat; followed by those associated with circularity such as resource utilization and efficiency in material life cycle assessment. These criteria with similar linked terms were gathered to create a search string and explore their interplay with social, environmental, economic and spatial aspects. The resultant articles were screened and selected by inclusion and exclusion criteria to review the articles thematically using inductive and deductive coding methods. Based on the study of the literature it is foreseen to gather evidences not only on the synergies and trade-offs but also on the state-of-the-art, materials and methods as well as addressal of societal challenges in transition towards sustainable urbanization. Thus, find first answers to the research question – how can circularity and resilience be achieved simultaneously while contributing towards sustainable urban transformation and contribute to develop a new research agenda covering both environmental risk and resources debate. Since the study is still underway, the authors intend to gather the results in due course and present them at the upcoming IOER Annual Conference in September.

Authors

Riyan Habeeb Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Regine Ortlepp Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Georg Schiller Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: A4
Format: Presentation
Track: 4. Circularity and resilience in building and settlement development

A4 – Drivers and barriers of social innovations for a circular built environment: insights from a case study design

There are many approaches to transitioning the built environment towards circular practices, i.e. slowing, closing, and narrowing resource flows, social innovations being a big field among them. Social innovations in the sense of new ways of doing, organizing, framing, and knowing complement technical innovations to achieve a systemic change. However, social innovations face a variety of barriers, and profit from as wide a field of benefits, strongly dependent on the respective context. This case study design looks into three exemplary social innovation approaches that follow different lines of the social innovation definition as well as different circularity strategies, to identify the most important barriers and enablers:

- Adaptive reuse of existing buildings through cooperative buying: an innovative ownership model (new ways of decision making) slowing resource flows.
- The (commercial) reuse of building materials and building parts represents new practices within the construction value chain, providing knowledge about reusable building materials, representing new ways of knowing, and both slowing and closing resource flows
- Using new technologies like 3D printing of buildings and building parts represents new practices and narrows resource flows
- Semi-structured expert interviews were conducted to gain initiators' and practitioners' insights, and evaluated using a qualitative approach.

The main findings differ between contexts: the initiating group: the cooperative buying groups included as well as one building parts reuse provider have an activist character. Their biggest barriers are access to financing of their projects as well as lack of support from governance structures, while they cite support from their network their biggest enabler. Business actors such as initiators of 3D printing in construction or building material platforms have more stable financing options, but lack the public awareness and trust in their ventures. However, they benefit from their technologies' innovativeness and the interest among their peers and target groups.

Authors

Katharina Bullinger Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: A4
Format: Presentation
Track: 4. Circularity and resilience in building and settlement development

A4 – Flood Damage – Connecting Costs and Material Needs for more sustainable Flood Preparedness

Flood risk analyses often focus only on damage costs to buildings (and other receptors exposed to risk). The HOWAD approach developed at IOER is doing the same based on depth-damage functions related to refurbishment costs. To extend the existing modeling approach, we now also consider damaged material quantities in case of flooding. The IOER material cadaster already includes related information to the building material that needs to be combined with the existing depth-damage functions for specific building types (based on building age/construction period and building structure). The approach then allows comparison of damage and material consumption for adapted vs non-adapted buildings. As an additional benefit, the procedure enables to compare these damage variants regarding global warming potential as a contribution to climate protection. The modelling provides new insights into a comprehensive consideration of precaution measures instead of refurbishment after a flood event. It might require less resources and would thus be more sustainable. It would help to support the circularity concepts of slowing (flood-resistant building materials have a longer lifetime) and narrowing (flood-resistant buildings need less materials) in the building sector. Material use and cost invested could thus be optimised.

Authors

Marco Neubert Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Reinhard Schinke Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Karin Gruhler Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Regine Ortlepp Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: A5
Format: Presentation
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

A5 – Comparative Study of Urban Planning Elements for Carbon Reduction: Public Acceptance in Germany and South Korea

This research aims to contribute to the establishment of carbon-neutral policies by comparing the public acceptance of urban planning elements and policies designed to reduce carbon footprints in South Korea and Germany. The study involves a comprehensive review of carbon footprint (CF) reduction research and policies in both nations, focusing on sector-specific planning elements related to food, housing, transportation, waste, and water consumption. The research methodology includes an initial investigation of policy issues and research trends, followed by defining the research scope and direction through expert consultations. Subsequent steps include examining CF reduction planning elements and policy initiatives, deriving sector-specific CF reduction elements using LangChain technology, and validating these elements and policy acceptance items through expert feedback. The study also conducts an analysis of public acceptance and perception types regarding sector-specific CF reduction planning elements and policies through online surveys targeting 500 individuals in South Korea and Germany, complemented by Q-methodology for investigating and analyzing perception types. The comparative analysis of survey results aims to identify differences in acceptance determinants based on perception types, using descriptive statistical analysis and structural equation modeling. The ultimate goal is to propose policy utilization strategies informed by the comparative analysis of acceptance and perception type survey outcomes.

Authors

Taehyun Kim Korea Environment Institute

Parallel Session: A5
Format: Presentation
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

A5 – Identifying Conservation Gap in Biodiversity Hotspot Areas: Single Flagship Species or Multi-species?

Protected areas (PAs) are expected to be a valuable tool to combat habitat loss and biodiversity decline. However, the effectiveness of many PAs around the world is questionable, because many PAs have been largely established without strategic or organized planning. To decide if existing PAs are adequately protecting the biodiversity and where the expansion of PAs is most needed to preserve biodiversity in the future, this paper selected Yunlong County, a typical area in a biodiversity hotspot in China, as an example, then 14 animal species are selected as the surrogate species. We modeled the potential distribution ranges for 14 species using the MaxEnt model, then assessed to what extent PAs in Yunlong County provide coverage for surrogate species. As the most noted local flagship species, *Rhinopithecus bieti* has long been considered as the target species of identifying PAs by many researches in Yunlong County. We carried out a conservation gap analysis using *Rhinopithecus bieti* as an indicator to examine to what degree surrogate species are represented by the conservation gap. According to The Global Biodiversity Framework's "30x30" Target, 30% percent of the county area is designated as the priority area. The results showed that current PAs only covered 22.55% of suitable habitat of surrogate species on average. The conservation gap identification using *Rhinopithecus bieti* and existing PAs combined cover 47.54% of surrogate species on average. According to habitat suitability simulation of multi-species, the prioritizing richness (ABF) scenario provides coverage of 79.89%; the prioritizing rarity (CAZ) scenario provides coverage of 76.30%. Based on the comparison results, we used the high-priority areas of the prioritizing richness (ABF) scenario and identified the conservation gap, then put forward protecting and managing measures to provide a helpful reference for biodiversity conservation.

Authors

Jing Gan Tongji University

Mo Wang Tongji University

Parallel Session: A5
Format: Presentation
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

A5 – Impact Mitigation for highways in the D-A-CH countries – legal basis, effectiveness of implementation and current challenges in the light of climate and landscape change

All three D-A-CH countries (Germany, Austria and Switzerland) have impact mitigation regulations in place to counterbalance the unavoidable impairments of nature and landscape resulting from infrastructure projects. Despite the long standing experiences, no systematic evaluation of the effectiveness and efficiency of compensation measures exists and their long term management remains a major challenge. To this adds a growing uncertainty due to the effects of climate and landscape change.

The presentation will build on the transnational research project "Compensation areas in transition" which is being carried out by an interdisciplinary and international project team from practice and science in the D-A-CH countries. The project aims for a presentation of the status quo and the development of recommendations for a future-proof compensation planning. The goal of the project is thus to inform practice across countries with regard to how the planning, safeguarding, maintenance and monitoring of compensation areas and measures can be improved in the future

The suggested outline of the talk includes the following aspects:

1. Brief comparison of the legal standards,
2. Implementation of compensation measures for infrastructure development – current state, tools and lessons learnt,
3. Challenges from climate and landscape change,
4. Recommendations.

Authors

Marianne Darbi Hochschule Geisenheim University

Nora Schmidt Hochschule Geisenheim University

Marius Werner Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Juliane Albrecht Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: A6
Format: Presentation
Track: 6. Open topic

A6 – Expression vs. Continuation. On a Necessary Transformation in the Epistemology and Methodology of Architectural Design.

How does a building look, that is in harmony with nature? What role does beauty play in designing harmonious environments? How do architects judge whether their designs possess these qualities or not?

In this contribution the epistemology that is at the core of the architectural design procedure will be subjected to a thorough criticism. I describe and analyze the paradigm used – unconsciously or not – by most architects as the paradigm of expression. With roots going back to antiquity, it is the prevailing approach to architectural design since the rise of modern functionalism about 100 years ago.

While its strength lies in producing spectacular individual works, it also exposes some critical weaknesses. The first of which is an inherent blindness to the relation of a building to its environment, for example a neighborhood or a city. Architects usually do consider urban context, but it is conceptually separated from architecture itself. The second weakness is, that to prove or disprove a design it can only proceed in an impressionistic manner, as opposed to a deliberative manner. If one wants to know what is true, within this paradigm, one cannot reason – one can only look at things.

What if the core notion of architecture was "continuity" instead of "expression"? What if professional communication in architecture, which is currently dominated by rituals of reverence and dependency on authorities, would be marked by a critical exchange of ideas? What if architects would empirically test design principles?

This is the necessary transformation in the epistemology and methodology of architecture. It will not only help to overcome fossil-capitalist design habits and to keep the construction of our habitat within the planetary boundaries. It will also make it easier to shape environments that are coherent, sustainable and even "in harmony with nature".

Authors

Paul Friedl Technische Universität Berlin

Parallel Session: A6
Format: Presentation
Track: 6. Open topic

A6 – Architecture of Subtraction: An Investigation on the Potential of the Concept of Subtraction in Transforming the Discipline of Architecture

The Anthropocene is a proposed term for the new geologic period in response to the dominant influence of human activities in the natural environment, which entails a complex discourse about climate and its expanded interconnection with socio-economic conditions. Architecture, with the medium of adding new structures and development under the construction-tied building sector, bears a significant responsibility in this anthropogenic narrative. Architects are increasingly tasked with a reverse approach: retrofitting existing structures, building upon what already exists, and advocating for designs that minimize new construction. Architectural additions are negated through the pursuit of subtraction. The premise of the presentation is that architecture and its associations with addition make this transformation towards an architecture of subtraction a challenge. Additionally, it presents a paradox, as the concept of addition inherently resonates with the essence of architecture and the built environment. Yet, the very act of constructing buildings, infrastructure, and urban development involves simultaneous resource, energy, and land subtraction.

The lecture presents different subtraction concepts in architecture along with already-existing potentials and past architectural examples, bringing together isolated subtraction discourses. The presentation concludes with the discovered similarities between the different interpretations of less, removal, and taking away that explain the consistency, nuances, and expandable possibilities of the concept of subtraction.

Authors

Kamille Kym Olympia De La Salle-College of Saint Benilde

Parallel Session: A6
Format: Presentation
Track: 6. Open topic

A6 – Every-pair interactions and their applications in spatial problems

Many processes taking place in space involve some sort of interaction. A site receives influence from another site, whereas in many cases the strength decreases with the distance. Every-pair interactions describe the sum of all influences that a site receives from any other site of the considered structure. The numerical quantification of the every-pair interactions is computationally demanding. Therefore, we provide an analytical expression for the case of a fractal structure and interactions that are given by a power of the Euclidean distance. We illustrate the every-pair interactions in two applications. First, it is well known that the Urban Heat Island (UHI) intensity increases with city size. However, it is discussed whether UHI intensity saturates or not. We describe the UHI intensity by means of every-pair interactions and do find a saturation for surface temperature. Second, dispersion of urban development is commonly described by a similar expression as the every-pair interactions – we explore implications.

Authors

Diego Rybski Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Fabiano L. Ribeiro Complexity Science Hub Vienna

Yunfei Li Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Martin Behnisch Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Abstracts

Parallel Sessions B

Parallel Session: B1
Format: Dialogue session
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

B1 – Space-related sufficiency strategies: Building blocks for transformation?

The future of humanity seems bleak: The double crisis of biodiversity loss and climate change is likely to have detrimental impacts on societies by inter alia threatening food security and infrastructure integrity. Therefore, calls for "living in harmony with nature" (Vision of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework 2023) and change is becoming ever louder – and urgent. But what does "living in harmony with nature" mean and how do we get there?

We will address these questions creatively and discursively in this dialogue session. Particular attention will be paid to the sufficiency strategy, especially to the question of which space-related sufficiency strategies can enable transformative change. The aim is to initiate a discourse on the various aspects of sufficiency, which, in addition to the absolute reduction of resource consumption and environmental pollution, can also include social justice and the question of a good life. Rather than aiming at finding solutions this session's objective is to uncover conflicts of interest and obstacles, recognise opportunities and to give impulses to approach sustainability from a different angle.

Schedule of the session

Preparation: The room is set up with about six group tables. There are flipcharts and material for the drawing/collage on each table. Posters on which tasks 1 and 2 and a brief overview of 'sufficiency' are written are pinned to a pinboard, but covered.

Introduction (5 minutes)

What does "living in harmony with nature" mean? (task 1) (15 minutes)

Content: Participants are asked how they imagine a "life in harmony with nature", i.e., what the goal of transformation is for them. They are asked to compile their thoughts in a collage/drawing.

Methods: Group formation; basis could be drawings of a globe, a section of a map, a landscape or a section of a city neighbourhood; the participants can write important key points next to the collage

Sufficiency and what it means: A short introduction. (5 minutes)

Content: Brief presentation of the concept of sufficiency as a sustainability strategy in contrast to consistency and efficiency – and the different aspects (can be supplemented by the participants if they wish)

Sufficiency and "living in harmony with nature" (task 2) (15 minutes)

Content: Discussion in the groups on the following questions:

1. Are there aspects of the drafted visions that are already related to sufficiency? If not, why not?

and:

2. What are sufficiency strategies that can enable and accelerate transformative change?

Method: Collection of considerations on a flipchart

Market of (sufficiency) possibilities and questions (15 minutes)

Content: Posters on the various visions and related discussions are displayed in the room. One or two people from a group stay with the poster, while the other participants can walk around freely, look at the results, discuss them and comment on them.

Methods: Posters remain on the tables or are hung up. Participants can write comments on moderation cards and pin them to the respective topic

Brief summary of the results (5 minutes)

Authors

Marianne Hachtmann Technische Universität Berlin

Parallel Session: B2
Format: Dialogue session
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

B2 – How to deal with the complexity of transformation processes in policy consulting: An exchange of experiences and methods

What effect do political instruments and measures have on transformation processes that are intended to support them? How do they influence different actors? To what extent are they accepted or rejected? And why is that the case? Do they trigger unintended or undesirable side effects? These are questions that arise for anyone developing and implementing policies, especially when they are intended to bring about or support societal transformations. At the beginning of the dialogue session, methods will be introduced to better capture the complex and social effects of policies in transformation processes. These methods better reflect the complexity present in reality than methods based on simple linear causality relationships. Overly simplified complexity is critical and often leads to misjudgements because certain factors or feedback loops have not been considered. Overly detailed complexity considerations are overwhelming and difficult to convey. After the brief impulse, there will be a direct exchange with the participants. The aim is to exchange experiences among participants of the session, who are familiar with methods for managing complexity in practice or have applied them themselves. Depending on the participants, the discussion may begin by narrowing down the subject area or governance level.

Authors

Christoph Schünemann Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: B3
Format: Short presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

B3 – Spatial tools to model a global transformation towards a bio-based built environment

Built environments contribute more than a third of global energy-related carbon emissions (UNEP 2023). In order to meet global climate targets, the sector needs to reverse its emission trajectories. One way of achieving this is to shift construction material input from carbon-intensive materials to bio-based regenerative products such as timber and bamboo, which have the potential to store significant amounts of carbon in the long term.

The transition towards a net-zero built environment could be advanced if materials are sourced from regional forests, considering the growing interest in ‘regionalising’ or ‘shortening’ supply chains to promote self-sufficiency and reduce climate impacts. We therefore propose a model to systematically quantify and match the supply of and demand for bio-based building materials for all urban agglomerates globally. A key feature of the model is to be spatially explicit, which will enable us to explore the potential for building material demand to be met by regional supplies.

The model is divided into the following components: on the supply side, it will use a statistical model to map potential timber production. In terms of demand, the model will use high-resolution earth observation datasets to quantify building stocks and typologies globally, which will enable us to estimate material demand for urban agglomerates. Future demand will be projected by considering various scenarios of socio-economic development, particularly with regards to future developments of floor area, distribution of building typologies, and the level of adoption of bio-based building materials. To match supply and demand, a spatially explicit supply-demand balance algorithm will be applied to identify regional forest areas needed to theoretically supply future urban construction materials. Finally, the model will quantify carbon sinks and substitution effects of a bio-based built environment using life-cycle assessment (LCA) approaches.

Authors

Adrian Foong Bauhaus der Erde gGmbH

Parallel Session: B3
Format: Short presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

B3 – From Traffic Data to Traffic Insights: A Case Study in Dresden

Traffic monitoring systems are essential in intelligent transportation systems for timely congestion and incident identification to optimize traffic flow and reduce congestion. In collaboration with the City of Dresden and the Saxon State Road Administration, we have developed the advanced urban traffic management system called VAMOS (Verkehrsanalyse-, Management- und Optimierungssystem) in Dresden over the past two decades. This system utilizes an extensive network of over 1,800 traffic detectors, including loops, infrared sensors, floating vehicles, and roadside units (RSUs) to facilitate around-the-clock traffic monitoring and management.

Large-scale historical traffic data in VAMOS supports valuable data-driven applications such as traffic state estimation, travel behavior modeling, policymaking, air and noise pollution analysis, and future urban traffic planning. However, this data often contains missing or incorrect entries due to connection loss, or detector malfunctions. In response, we have developed a deep learning-based imputation model called LSUTDI (Large-Scale Urban Traffic Data Imputer) to process and impute all missing and anomalous entries, ensuring a more accurate, reliable, and ready-to-use dataset.

Our pilot study on the imputed dataset investigates trends in daily travel behaviors for cars and heavy vehicles within Dresden, identifying congestion hotspots. This provides insights into traffic flow patterns and potential bottlenecks in peak and off-peak traffic hours, as well as during workdays and holidays. Additionally, the analysis reveals route choice behaviors during large gatherings, football matches, and similar occasions.. Furthermore, we analyzed the distribution of different vehicle types in Dresden in both space and time.

In support of the net-zero carbon transition, further research should focus on measuring, modelling, and analysing vehicle exhaust and noise emissions caused by different types of vehicles. This will help the city to quantify, predict, and reduce traffic emissions. Analyzing multimodal mobility patterns and travel behavior is also important for planning and managing a sustainable urban traffic system.

Authors

Jyotirmaya Ijaradar Technische Universität Dresden

Matthias Korner Technische Universität Dresden

Meng Wang Technische Universität Dresden

Sebastian Pape Technische Universität Berlin

Parallel Session: B4
Format: Presentation
Track: 4. Circularity and resilience in building and settlement development

B4 – Crafting Urban Resilience and Circular Economy: Insights from Open Labs in the FabCity Initiative Hamburg

In the face of climate change and other global crises, urban resilience has been increasingly discussed as a normative goal for cities and is linked to sustainability (Meerow et al. 2016). Similarly, circular economy (CE) has been assigned a great deal of potential in transformation and sustainability discussions, but remains elusively defined (Kirchherr et al. 2023). Criticism of CE frequently asks whether it truly contributes to sustainability socially, ecologically, or economically (Corvellec et al. 2021). Spatial development and integration of spaces for circularity are essential to CE implementation in cities and sustainability goals (Tsui et al. 2021).

The FabCity Global Initiative is an example of an effort to address CE and resilience concerns simultaneously (Diez 2018; Diez et al. 2019). Within this conceptual framework, Open Labs are a key strategic instrument for the CE transition and of urban resilience infrastructure (Tatum/Knieling 2024), providing physical spaces for innovation, experimentation, and production by private citizens, entrepreneurs, educators, and community groups. They act as small-scale testbeds for alternative and parallel structures to the linear economy and testing new forms of decision-making (Daniell et al. 2011).

This paper draws on research performed within the project “FabCity: Decentral, digital production for value creation” (funded by dtec.bw, NextGenerationEU) in Hamburg. Based on case studies of two Open Labs (as part of the Hamburg FabCity Initiative), we identify the informal instruments these actors apply to negotiate the attainment of their goals within the existing governance and regulatory systems. We argue that the successful implementation of CE and, respectively, positive effects on urban resilience in the long term will require the formalization of these instruments for innovation and experimentation within spatial development policy and governance frameworks.

Authors

Merle Ibach HafenCity University Hamburg

Kimberly Tatum HafenCity University Hamburg

Parallel Session: B4
Format: Presentation
Track: 4. Circularity and resilience in building and settlement development

B4 – Negotiating Biophysical Limits of the Bioeconomy in EU Policy

The dominant bioeconomy discourse seeks a large-scale substitution of fossil fuels and materials to tackle multiple crises. However, raising biomass demand in the European Union can increase global pressure on land and resources, causing social-ecological conflicts and aggravating crisis dynamics. Thus, it is crucial to evaluate the transformative potential of the bioeconomy by the extent to which it addresses biophysical limits. While increasing quantitative monitoring of the bioeconomy is vital, it is also necessary to thoroughly examine competing interests in shaping policy development.

In my presentation, I will contribute to this endeavor by providing insights into our qualitative study. By conducting semi-structured interviews and analyzing position papers, we examined how competing actor constellations address biophysical limits in two conflicts on regulating cascading use and bio-based plastics. We analyzed EU policy documents to understand to what extent these actor constellations could assert their positions and strategies.

Our results indicate that actors supporting a circular and sufficiency-oriented bioeconomy could discursively inscribe their reading of biophysical limits in EU policies on bio-based plastics and bioenergy. However, we demonstrate that the extent to which this diagnosis of biophysical limits translates into measures restricting biomass mobilization diverges between the two conflicts. While generally supporting bio-based plastics, the current EU policy aims to reduce plastics, especially in single-use applications, and increase the circularity of production systems instead of a mere substitution with biomass. In contrast, actors supporting a growth-based bioeconomy could hinder a restrictive implementation of cascading use, risking increasing pressure on agricultural land, forests, and other ecosystems.

Ultimately, by understanding the EU bioeconomy policy as a contested field, we shed light on its potential and hurdles for social-ecological transformations.

Authors

Benjamin Fleischmann BOKU University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna

Parallel Session: B5
Format: Presentation
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

B5 – A long-term ecological perspective and its integration with local knowledge is a requisite for sustainable regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity

Achieving food security while maintaining biodiversity is a major challenge for many Global South (GS) nations that are threatened by ongoing climate change with serious implications for livelihoods of billions. Given the long histories of human influence and past climatic changes collectively shaping today's GS landscapes, it is imperative to incorporate both ecological and cultural legacies in their planning and management. Conservation and restoration plans often fail to acknowledge the significance of such legacies, resulting in conflicts between restoration targets and people's needs. For example, management policies that are regulatory and/or restrictive in nature (e.g. fire prevention, monoculture afforestation) often contrast with traditional practices supporting local livelihoods, while undermining the crucial role of past ecological processes. Amid ongoing loss of traditional knowledge, resource extraction and state intervention deep-rooted in colonialism, synergies between long-term ecology and local/Indigenous knowledge can effectively support landscape conservation targets in the GS (e.g. identification of natural and biocultural heritage components) that maximize biodiversity and resilience in ecosystems. Such undertaking underlines the need for interactive spaces for scientific and stakeholder communities to achieve balanced landscape scenarios. Here we bring an example of such network, Past Global Changes (PAGES)'s DiverseK Working Group, that merges diverse knowledge systems for producing a cross-disciplinary evidence base for practical yet inclusive decision-making on environmental and societal issues of the day. We explicitly elaborate on a compelling case of age-old Indian agroforestry systems at the heart of a human-dominated biodiversity hotspot, where the long-term perspective unfolds the social-ecological consequences of traditional land management (effect of fire practices on local plant diversity; people's historic role in forest conservation via adopting agroecology). At the backdrop of India's National Agroforestry Policy, the case study offers region-specific conservation-restoration strategies rooted in careful, evidence-based incorporation of local practices, with positive implications for human-influenced GS landscapes at large.

Authors

Charuta Kulkarni Indian Institute of Technology Madras

Qiaoyu Cui Chinese Academy of Sciences

Estelle Razanatsoa University of Cape Town

Laurent Marquer University of Innsbruck

Michal Slowinski Polish Academy of Sciences

Parallel Session: B5
Format: Presentation
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

B5 – Assessing the Drought and Heat Risks for Urban Green Infrastructure: Case of Plauen, Germany

More frequent and intense drought and heat events imply increasing drought and heat multi-risks for urban green infrastructure (UGI) and their ecosystem services (ES). Given the significance of UGI towards urban resilience and biodiversity, analyzing and evaluating these multi-risks is a prerequisite for taking adequate action in planning and managing UGI. Therefore, this research applies and tests the Drought and Heat Risk Assessment (DHR) Framework and methodology on the example of Hammer Park in Plauen, Germany, through a set of spatiotemporal indicators, and assesses the risks for selected ES. First, the risk system is delineated with its hazard, exposure and vulnerability components, determining which indicators are relevant for representing the system. Local stakeholders with expertise in urban planning, UGI management, nature/biodiversity protection, water management, climate/meteorology, soil science, environmental engineering, and tourism and culture, are invited for a workshop to select indicators, and set their evaluation criteria with weights and thresholds. Subsequently, the risk indicators are calculated using multiple methods such as models, remote sensing, GIS analysis, and measurement stations. Using the TOPSIS method, the calculated risk indicators are evaluated based on their distance from the ideal and non-ideal situations, and aggregated within the provisioning, regulating, and cultural dimensions of ES. The resulting information is provided in the form of sub-city spatial maps that can also display temporal variability (e.g., monthly or seasonal). The risk assessment supports decision makers in judging on the risks for UGI's ES under changing conditions, and implement risk-reduction alternatives to protect the benefits they provide for the society and environment.

Authors

Raghid Shehayeb Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development /
Technische Universität Dresden

Regine Ortlepp Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Jochen Schanze Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development /
Technische Universität Dresden

Parallel Session: B5
Format: Presentation
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

B5 – Land Transitions and Socio-Ecological Restructuring at the Urban-rural Interface: A Case Study of Huangyan/Taizhou in China

In the urban rural interface, urbanization processes have drastically impacted its ecological system as well as culture and social networks. The achievement of global development aims such as the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is now seen to depend largely on the level of cooperation between territories and actors across different urban and rural geographies. In our article, take Huangyan in China as a living lab, we consider how the social-ecological impacts of land transition affect and are affected by the everyday practices of local residents.

To understand trends in land transition with a focus on ecosystem restructuring, we analyzed changes in land cover and land use (LCLU) between 2010 and 2020 using GIS methods. During the field survey on 2019, 2023 and 2024, participant observation as well as in-depth interviews with planning professionals, local authorities and residents were conducted to identify the social meanings of land use changes.

The study shows a clear trend of urbanization in the past ten years, with urban land cover expanding by approximately 72%. Other types of land cover were declined by varying degrees during the same period. The largest decrease was seen in grassland, which contracted by 60%. Through our field investigations, we observed that some planned grassland along the roads/streets and currently vacant lands located close to the residential areas were informally used for growing vegetables.

We found that with formally designed urban green space, the informal use of land at the urban rural interface, such as for planting vegetables, presents new insight for ecosystem services and urban planning. Changes in land use are both the cause and consequence of socio-ecological change. While the physical changes occurring within rural-urban transformations do not necessarily entail simultaneous social changes, space is constantly being reshaped by local daily activities.

Authors

Suili Xiao Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Huang Huang Tongji University

Parallel Session: B6
Format: Dialogue session
Track: 6. Open topic

B6 – Imaginaries of inside-out place making: sensing, designing and transforming (urban) spaces with humans and the non-human world for sustainable and climate resilient futures

This session is organised as a facilitated workshop enabling participants to engage with each other in order to brainstorm and ideate co-creatively. The three convenors will be moderating through the various phases of the workshop working in pairs, groups, plenary. Outcome: highlighting a rather neglected, at best implicit topic; connecting discourses from global south and global north about imaginaries; learning from each other's perspectives, cross-culturally; networking from across the world; an immersion. Research and action related to inner transformation has gained traction in recent years as a field in sustainability, climate science, and global policy. For the first time, the topic has also been included in the AR6 WIIII of the IPCC. This relatively new field draws conceptually from a wide range of theories and models, including e.g. Theory U, Integral Theory, Resonance Theory, deep leverage points, biopoetics, the environmental humanities, non-western philosophies, and indigenous wisdom. Existing research does not explicitly consider the relationship of inner transformation with the urban development processes that dramatically transform natural landscapes and diverse ecosystem habitats. Yet urbanization is the single most global transformative process that defines the next 30 years. With this workshop we intend to open up an uncommon perspective and approach to access and understand the complex relationships of the human(-made) and non-human worlds with the aim to identify potentials and options for transformative change towards regenerative and resilient futures. Virtually in the spirit of Carl Jung, who wrote in his 'Memories, Dreams, Reflections', "At times I feel as if I am spread out over the landscape and inside things, and am myself living in every tree, in the splashing of the waves, in the clouds, and the animals that come and go, in the procession of seasons". Can we possibly feel and sense the same like Jung – for the human made and designed places/spaces especially by integrating these with the non-human world? How can individual, socio-cultural, and system transformation for place-making and human well-being happen? The participants will engage themselves playing with the parameters of deep transformation viz., cross-culture; inter-and trans-disciplinarity; relationship between human (inner beings)-nature-built environment; and inner worlds (w.r.t geographies, emotions, spirituality, beliefs, faith, and other inner dimensions of our existence).

The dialogue session will be broadly structured along the process of

1. Introduction by convenors;
2. Taking stock and discuss approaches, sharing experiences and ideas using prompts (facilitation: contemplation, dialogue, dyadic interaction);
3. (Re-)Imagining place/space-making from the inside-out (facilitation: break out groups);

4. Brief harvest of group work results and closing

Authors

Christoph Woiwode Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development /
URBNANCE / Indo-German Centre for Sustainability / Indian Institute of Technology Madras

Keya Chakraborty Srishti Manipal Institute of Art, Design and Technology, India

Lalit Kishor Bhati PATH Architects & Planners; Co-Founder: Auroville Campus Initiative (ACI);
Coordinator: Auroville Integral Sustainability Institute, India

Abstracts

Parallel Sessions C

Parallel Session: C1
Format: Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

C1 – Discursive greening: local political debates in urban greening and biodiversity planning and implementation in German and Italian municipalities

Nature is considered a potent ally in combating climate change in cities. To unleash its power, the European Union has been promoting the use of nature in cities since the EU Green Deal in 2019 and is further elaborated in the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 in the subsequent year. Important targets to protect and improve biodiversity in cities are set to be achieved through specific actions on the ground, such as nature-based solutions (NbS). Specifically, the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 elaborates on the so-called Urban Greening Plan (UGP), a recommended planning instrument for municipalities with more than 20.000 inhabitants to manage green urban spaces and biodiversity. Yet, exploratory research has revealed obstacles in implementing such plans, as coherent financial and legislative support from the EU and the national governments is absent (Costadone and Vierikko 2023). On this premise, the paper proposes to analyse the political debates at the local level on the implementation of UGP in two European countries, Germany and Italy. These two countries represent the northern and southern politico-economic models while presenting fundamentally similar planning structures. Therefore, the paper aims to answer the following research question: which discourses and actors are recognisable in implementing UGP to integrate human-nature relationships in planners' everyday actions? Through the discourse network analysis methodology (DNA), the authors analyse local newspaper articles and UGP to identify discourse coalitions to highlight 1) main arguments and concepts associated in favour or against urban nature, 2) different meanings attributed to nature and the consequent actions, and 3) key actors able to 'connect the dots' between the local and the EU level. The results of this research aim to spotlight the reasons behind the (in)action of local planning actors and their agency in bringing nature to the centre of the everyday.

Authors

Alessandro Arlati HafenCity Universität Hamburg

Parallel Session: C1
Format: Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

C1 – Pond of liquid bodies. A resonance artificial landscape through acoustic agreements and vibrant evidences, based on imagist poems

Imagist literature shows how a string of words produces unexpected sonorities and meanings that inspire creative choices (Molensky 2007). For example, T.S. Eliot's *Four Quartets* (1943), refers to unconventional traits ("breathing light"); the value of sound ("the silence in which lotuses rise"); remnants of life ("whalebone, starfish"); or acoustic distances ("echoing memory of footsteps"). These references are used for an educational interdisciplinary project promoted by the University of Alicante (Spain) in these times where data, generative methods and cartographies take you to remote places from which you can be sensitive to issues such as social disparities or natural scarcities.

Physical layouts are achieved through acoustic agreements and vibrant matter experiments (Ripley 2007, Bennett 2010) negotiating for whom or with whom their statements make sense: "after the storm the birds return and the river carries sediments", "the species of the night wake up", "some artificial sounds dialogue with other natural ones", etc. "Pond of liquid bodies" is the name for the general arrangement of the exhibition space (January 2024).

The method is similar to how a text-image generative artificial intelligence works, as it starts with the language structure, finds a formal/spatial/sound meaning from strings of words, transposes that meaning to a different space-time, makes adjustments to the attributes, achieves visual (image, or digital fabrication) results, and creates alternatives in a natural way (Florian 2023). The philosophy of aesthetic resonance provides an attitude and strategies that AI cannot achieve: to feel stimulated by a collective assignment, inspired in the search for referents, sometimes lost, or satisfied to perceive those resonant patterns in literature and vibrant material links that stand out among the physical devices (Rosa 2016, 370). And the fact is that, for now, AI is not ready to foresee the unavailability of the resonant world that surrounds us.

Authors

Jose Carrasco University of Alicante

Sara Prieto University of Alicante

Jose Antonio Sánchez-Fajardo University of Alicante

Parallel Session: C1
Format: Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

C1 – Planning the urban greening: is it a standardised necessity or a necessary evil, the case of Samsun

Urban green spaces play a crucial role in the wellbeing, livelihood, and environmental sustainability of cities, driving extensive research interest (Haaland et al., 2015; Nikolaidou et al., 2016; Fischer et al., 2018; Russo et al., 2018; Boulton et al., 2020; Gül et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2021). However, rapid urbanization and densification, alongside misguided planning strategies aimed at maximizing urban rent, often lead to the loss of green areas, diminishing urban quality of life. Despite standardized greenery obligations in planning regulations, tactical actions are sometimes employed to circumvent these standards or provide green spaces in a passive manner, minimizing their public utility.

In Turkey, green areas are planned based on population size, settlement characteristics, topography, natural features, and climatic conditions (Ersoy, 2016). However, neoliberal economic policies since the 1980s have prioritized urban rent over public welfare, resulting in rent-oriented urban development plans that compromise green space provision (Tekeli, 2014). Consequently, questions arise regarding the location, size, and quality of urban green spaces. This study investigates the qualitative and quantitative aspects of green spaces in Samsun Province's central districts: Atakum, İlkadım, Canik, and Tekkeköy. By examining the capacity and accessibility of urban green spaces in these districts, the research seeks to compare current land use patterns with approved planning decisions across different scales. Interviews with Metropolitan and district municipality planners and private sector planners involved in spatial planning for Samsun complement this analysis. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for guiding future urban planning to enhance urban environments and promote sustainability.

Authors

Tugce Sanli Ondokuz Mayıs University

Onur Genc Ondokuz Mayıs University

Yeliz Emecen *Ondokuz Mayıs University*

Parallel Session: C2
Format: Dialogue session
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

C2 – Speaking as proxy for Nature: A multispecies role-play on conflicts in urban energy transitions

Cities worldwide are switching to 100% renewable energy. However, the ecological impact of such projects on landscapes and biodiversity are often neglected. This raises new challenges for urban planning, which must attempt to better harmonise the needs of human and more-than-human nature. We therefore ask whether these challenges can be used to broaden anthropocentric notions of justice in the city towards multispecies and ecological justice?

In this session, we invite participants to role-play a land use conflict in Dresden. A solar farm has been proposed on the Elbe meadow. But no one asked the more-than-human inhabitants! The participants receive the game material including role cards representing more-than-human interests connected to the land. The aim of the game is to prepare a counter-proposal to the project, in which the participants act as representatives for more-than-human concerns. At the end, the participants will share their reflections on the dilemmas they have experienced and the ideas they have developed. This session is limited to 18 participants. The organisers will provide role cards and other accessories to immerse yourself in the role play together. The session is planned for 90 minutes.

Authors

Philip Harms Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Neelakshi Joshi Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: C3
Format: Presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

C3 – The IOER Research Data Centre – data, simulations and tools for the sustainable transformation of neighbourhoods, cities, and regions

The Research Data Centre (IOER RDC) of the Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER) is an important milestone in supporting sustainable transformative urban and regional development. The IOER RDC offers spatial data, analyses and digital tools that enable interdisciplinary research, support policy and planning practice and facilitate decision-making for spatial sustainability transformations. It offers high-resolution indicator maps on land use, ecosystems, settlement structures and building stock as well as cross-scale and cross-disciplinary spatial analyses, modelling and simulations. These tools will help policy makers and planners to understand the potential impacts of different development scenarios, recognise trade-offs and make informed decisions that support sustainable urban and regional development. The article presents the IOER RDC and its products on the topics of land use, settlements, buildings and ecosystems.

Authors

Maria Nieswand Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Tobias Krüger Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Claudia Dworczyk Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Sujit Sikder Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Reinhard Schinke Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Alexander Dunkel Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: C3
Format: Presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

C3 – Semantic data model for municipal landscape planning in Germany: An approach for modelling landscape planning content in data standards

The provision of green spaces and green structures is one of the central tasks of local municipalities. Their protection and development is presented in local landscape plans and open space structure plans. Landscape plans also identify land use conflicts and define measures for the sustainable management of urban areas. The contents of landscape planning are therefore an important basis for spatial planning. However, the export to a standardised plan graphic leads to a loss of information. Data standards can counteract this challenge as they standardise communication and provide a uniform data structure. By using a standardised language, data standards can improve workflows and the provision of information. In Germany, the XPlanung data standard was introduced as mandatory in 2023. The field now faces the challenge of mapping its content in XPlanung.

Although general transferability to the data standard has been proven, not all content can be described in XPlanung. There is a considerable need for development in order to standardise landscape planning information with regard to the structural and technical requirements of XPlanung.

The research is dedicated to the semantic description of municipal landscape planning and its transfer into a digital planning language. Based on a nationwide analysis of landscape plans, the contents were transferred into a digital data model. This was followed by a multi-stage evaluation process in which the content was correlated, clustered and structured. The result is a proposal for a data model that can serve as a basis for the further development of XPlanung.

Authors

Benedikt Taiber Federal agency for nature conservation

Parallel Session: C3
Format: Presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

C3 – Influences of land use structure on well-being within the context of urban areas

Humans have an evolutionary bond with nature. The biophilia hypothesis, formulated by Edward O. Wilson in 1984, has also been examined by the World Health Organization (WHO) and more recently in science. However, previous research addressing urban land use and its composition and configuration is mostly based on cross-sectional data and lacks in identifying causal relationships regarding different aspects of land use structure. The possibility of using longitudinal data to record developments in this regard over time and to identify causal effects has not yet been studied extensively. The paper contributes to this research gap by analysing longitudinal data that record developments over time and the analysis of causal effects by using propensity score matching. A relationship between individual life satisfaction and mental health on the one hand and composition and configuration of urban land use on the other is established. There are several theories suggesting how landscape patterns affect human well-being. For example, the prospect-refuge theory implies a universal preference for savanna-like views. As well, environmental factors such as air quality might be affected by composition and fragmentation. Also, bird diversity is related to land use structure. On the other hand, there is evidence that air pollution and birdsong soundscapes positively affect life satisfaction and mental health. Urban land use is assessed by classification while composition and configuration are measured by landscape metrics. Both well-being indicators are recorded based on an analysis of the panel survey data sets of the Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP). The European Urban Atlas (EUA) of the Copernicus program is used as the data basis for investigating urban land use structure within German cities. The results have important implication for well-being policies in the context of urban planning.

Authors

Lukas Spatz Justus Liebig University Giessen

Parallel Session: C4
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools of transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalization

C4 – Assessing use of urban green spaces to inform planning for biodiversity and equitable access

Urban densification is an important goal for city planning to reduce the pressure of urban sprawl on natural ecosystems. However, resilient cities also need to provide equitable access to green spaces for human well-being and at the same time leave room for biodiversity. Since the COVID-19 pandemic, increasing attention is being given to urban green spaces and their use and accessibility as an indicator for what is important to city dwellers. For global comparison, we conducted a systematic review of urban green spaces use during and after the COVID-19 lockdowns. Our analysis reveals a surprisingly large discrepancy in the use of green spaces in different parts of the world which we can largely attribute to financial prosperity. However, a comparison of different methods to assess green space use is still lacking and it remains unclear if different methods lead to different results. In this paper, we will re-analyze our comprehensive systematic review dataset derived from 178 studies in 5 languages, covering 60 countries. We will categorize the methods ranging from counts on the ground, surveys and GPS tracking to social media analyses and Google mobility data. We will assess if these different methods lead to contrasting outcomes in detecting increases and decreases in green space use. We will further differentiate between different types of green spaces such as parks, forests, and gardens. Using access to green spaces as an indicator for resilient urban futures will allow further analyses of how to achieve equity in access to green spaces. To counter the apparent shortage in green spaces, urban planning cannot rely exclusively on counting park users, but needs to make best use of diverse methods to assess accessibility to all kinds of natural areas in and around cities.

Authors

Fritz Kleinschroth Leibniz Universität Hannover

Parallel Session: C4
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

C4 – Do fragile urban systems intensify urban vulnerability? An inquiry into the case of Mongla port municipality of Bagerhat district of Bangladesh

The contemporary concept of Climate Change Hotspot (CCH) identifies locations with vulnerable communities where impacts of climate change are exacerbated due to its poor planning practice and socio-economic condition. The experiences of climate change in urban areas widely vary because of spatial attributes of a geographical location which are formed with its infrastructure typologies and the general settings of urban environment. The port city Mongla is no exception of this analogy. For enhancing the well-being of urban populations in Mongla, the study aims to identify CCHs as places with risk exposures due to extreme and non-extreme impacts of climate change. Following a case study method, Mongla Port Municipality has been selected as a climate vulnerable coastal town of Bangladesh for investigating its spatial attributes identifying climate impacted fragile urban systems, and understanding multifaceted vulnerability through mapping CCHs to enhance urban resilience in face of recurrent natural and anthropogenic disasters.

Authors

Tasfin Aziz BRAC University Bangladesh

Parallel Session: C4
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

C4 – An Urban Rivers Renaissance? Stream restoration and Green-Blue Infrastructure in Latin America – Insights from urban planning in Colombia

While river restoration has become mainstream in the Global North, Latin American rivers have largely remained overlooked. In Colombia, a paradigm shift is underway, with an increasing integration of green-blue infrastructure and nature-based solutions in cities. We conducted a comparative policy analysis of strategic master plans in seven Colombian cities, revealing a surge in restoration initiatives beyond previous reports. The growing popularity of urban stream restoration is a promising approach to recover lost ecological processes, reconnect citizens with nature, and build more resilient cities. However, our analysis indicates a tendency towards unbalanced restoration goals, with a preference for recreational spaces, urban greening, and disaster risk reduction, while objectives related to participation, equity, and inclusion are often neglected. This is particularly concerning in the Latin American context, burdened by environmental injustice legacies and high vulnerability to climate change. Colombia has a national planning standard mandating cities to acknowledge the urban Ecological Structure, providing a robust foundation for protecting, restoring, and integrating urban nature within local land-use plans. Citizen and grassroots organization have been crucial in this process, defending and reappropriating urban commons, such as rivers and wetlands. The Colombian case provides valuable policy insights for Global South cities aspiring to undertake comprehensive urban river restoration. On the one hand, our analysis identifies several policy advancements aligned with key principles of nature-based solutions, including multifunctionality, ecological connectivity, cross-scale integration, and participatory governance. On the other, it highlights the dangers of depoliticized resilience, greening, and restoration agendas, as well as the fundamental role of citizen participation and environmental activism in shaping sustainable and just cities.

Authors

Gonzalo Pradilla Leibniz Universität Hannover

Parallel Session: C6
Format: Dialogue session
Track: 6. Open topic

C6 – Shifting the Paradigm: Situating South-North climate adaptation research collaborations in the intersection of equity and decolonisation

While the bilateral research collaborations between South and North become the apparent way towards just and sustained sustainable regions, the legacy of colonialism continues to shape contemporary North-South collaborations, particularly in research on spatial sustainability. These collaborations often reflect a pervasive 'white gaze,' (Pailey 2020) which imposes Western paradigms of progress and development onto diverse contexts, perpetuating structural inequalities rooted in historical power imbalances. These are further marred by a dominance of Western knowledge brokerage and an implicit mindset that measures development, e.g., of cities, climate agendas and socio-economic and cultural processes through a 'Western conceptualisation of worldly development' (Pailey 2020).

The conflicts in these so-called collaborative efforts can also be witnessed in the ongoing debates with one side pressuring the 'Developing countries' to do more for climate action, while the other argues on the historical exploitation and current need for growth as factors in less equal efforts. However, the recent IPCC report (IPCC 2022) has for the first time highlighted the role of ongoing colonialism as a key driver of climate change, underscoring the interconnectedness of environmental degradation and historical patterns of exploitation and domination. In this context, (Global) urban development can either reinforce existing power imbalances or serve as a tool for dismantling colonial structures, depending on how it is wielded and distributed.

Against this backdrop, we propose a 90-minute round table session that explores strategies for approaching South-North research collaborations, specifically climate adaptation collaborations, by situating it in the intersection of equity and decolonisation. We will invite two to three speakers from research and practice backgrounds involved in such collaborative projects. The discussion will seek to bring forth the nuances of the power dynamics that dictate these collaborations. Key themes for discussion include reimagining climate adaptation and mitigation efforts through a decolonial lens, empowering Southern researchers for equitable partnerships and exploring if there can be a new manifesto for South-North collaborations., grounded in equity and transcending the legacies of colonialism.

References:

IPCC. 2022. Climate Change – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability: Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. 1st ed. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844>.

Pailey, Robtel Neajai. 2020. "De-Centring the 'White Gaze' of Development." *Development and Change* 51 (3): 729–45. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dech.12550>.

Authors

Abhijeet Chandel TU Delft, Netherlands

Subhashree Nath Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Dhanasree Jayaram Manipal University, India

Oliver Lah TU Berlin

Abstracts

Parallel Sessions D

Parallel Session: D1
Format: Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

D1 – Urban human-nature partnership – a positive vision for planning post-anthropocentric cities

The transgression of planetary boundaries is harming the Earth's life-support systems. In a rapidly urbanizing world shaped by anthropocentric planning approaches, ideas and actions are necessary on how to set societal limits of making Nature materially and immaterially available. This requires further exploration of which sustainability-aligned values sharpen our conceptual understanding of how the limits of Nature's availability can be acknowledged and, particularly, operationalized in a real-life context such as urban planning.

In this presentation, we argue that limits of Nature's availability can be conceptualized through the vision of a human-nature partnership. To advance this vision, we further develop the theory of Unverfügbarkeit (English literally meaning unavailability) by the German sociologist Hartmut Rosa. Rosa's work provides a conceptual basis how respecting limits of Nature's availability can be approached along the cascade of making Nature useable, manageable, reachable, and visible. The objectives of this talk are twofold. First, we identify based on partnership ethics and the phenomenon of "Unverfügbarkeit" broad values feeding into the positive vision of a human-nature partnership. Second, we translate these guiding principles into four sub-visions that support urban planning to operationalize human-nature partnership.

A non-anthropocentric planning for urban human-nature partnership encompasses four sub-visions: The regenerative city respects limits of Nature's usability, based on the broad values of reciprocity, regeneration and solidarity. The healthy city promotes limits of Nature's manageability, nourished by broad values such as relational health, kinship, and justice. The mindful city honours limits of Nature's accessibility fostering an engaged meeting with Nature informed by care, place-based identities and mindfulness. Finally, the cordial city considers limits of Nature's visibility based on empathy and compassion towards Nature and our spiritual bonding with her. Along a social-ecological-technological system perspective, we will illustrate these sub-visions with practical examples of their implementation in and through urban planning.

Authors

Martina Artmann Weihenstephan-Triesdorf University of Applied Sciences / Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Philip Harms Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: D1
Format: Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

D1 – Dimensions and practices of cultural-spiritual human-nature (re)connection in Chennai, India

Humanity is facing a severe environmental crisis and cities are at the heart of the sustainability debate. Current approaches to urban sustainability are criticized for focusing merely on exterior dimensions of change. Such approaches are not considered sufficient in bringing about the necessary behavioral changes. In recent years, scholars in sustainability research have shifted increasing attention towards inner transformation approaches that address human dimensions like individual and collective worldviews, beliefs, values, and associated internal capacities.

In search of the driving forces for human-nature relationships and of new paradigms for sustainable development, spirituality and non-Western worldviews have received increasing attention over the past years. However, our knowledge about the role of spirituality in people's relationship with nature and in reorienting people towards nature is still limited especially in urban contexts, and current research is showing a strong bias towards Western cultural settings and conceptualizations of spirituality. In the local context of Chennai, India, we studied relationships urban dwellers have with nature, which role spirituality and culture play in these relationships and which (spiritual and cultural) experiences with nature might contribute to reconnecting citizens with nature.

Empirical research was conducted by applying a combination of ethnographic methods, including participant and non-participant observation, semi-structured interviews and group discussions. The research results reveal a wide variety of ways in which Chennai's inhabitants form relationships with nature. The findings further suggest that spirituality and culture play an important role in fostering human-nature connectedness. Spirituality, in particular, seems to act as major driving force for pro-environmental behavior and committed action for nature. Based on these findings, the integration of spiritual and cultural values is suggested as essential part of an integral and relational approach to urban sustainability. Consequently, we also propose various potential options of interventions for such integration in urban development practice.

Authors

Christoph Woiwode Leibniz Institute for Ecological Urban and Regional Developments/ Indo-German Centre for Sustainability at IIT Madras

Katrin Bernard Duisburg-Essen University

Parallel Session: D1
Format: Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

D1 – Building Environmental and Community Resilience through Active Citizenship: From Theory to Practice

Citizenship, as a fundamental social institution, is comprised of membership, rights, and duties. Environmental citizenship, more specifically, focuses on civic participation of individuals and groups to examine environmental problems, take action, and support healthy ecosystems and human-nature relationships. This presentation will focus on the concept of citizenship and the ways environmental challenges such as climate change, water quality, land use, species loss, urbanization, and energy development can relate to governance systems and social connection. Through efforts to educate, inform, and influence, citizens affect critical decisions related to environmental and community sustainability ranging from local to global scales. Voting, engaging in political processes, protest, organizational participation, volunteerism, citizen science, purchasing behavior, and art are some forms of citizen action.

Based on a new citizenship course at a large university in the midwestern United States, the presentation will address different theoretical perspectives of environmental citizenship and frameworks for civic participation. Additionally, examples of case study applications will be included, with emphasis on bridging rural-urban and other societal divides that prevent meaningful solutions. The overall objective will be to encourage educators, researchers, and planners to think more critically about citizenship, create places of citizenship, and promote practices of intentional citizenship that can help create more resilient ecological and social systems.

Authors

Kristi Lekies Ohio State University

Jason Parker Ohio State University

Keely Fisher Ohio State University

Parallel Session: D2
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

D2 – Factors promoting the creation and development of regional parks and green belts – a policy process perspective

Regional parks are an important policy tool for providing a wide range of ecosystem services, whether through the protection and ecological enhancement of landscapes, or the provision of cycling and walking routes for the direct experience of nature in conurbations. However, the adoption and implementation of regional park strategies require conflictual political decisions about the allocation of space, financial and human resources in complex urban regional governance contexts. The presentation examines the conditions under which regional park strategies are most likely to succeed. It draws on the well-established Multiple Streams Framework from political science, which posits that five crucial elements need to be taken into account (Kingdon 1984).

A policy change, e.g. the establishment of a regional park, depends on three streams which, at least to a large extent, live a life of their own. The problem stream reflects the intensity with which a problem is perceived. The policy stream contains proposals for solving problems, such as policy ideas, strategies or instruments. In the politics stream, which is characterised by staff turnover, policy makers take into account the voice of interest groups and the mood of the population. All three streams must be favourable at the same time and converge in a policy window, which is the fourth element. The fifth element, a committed and skilled policy entrepreneur, helps to link the streams by trying to convince current policy makers that a regional park is the best policy to solve current pressing problems.

The presentation explores this framework and illustrates the interplay of factors using the examples of the Leipzig Green Belt and the RheinMain Regional Park. It then discusses the explanatory power of the framework and its limitations. Finally, the presentation considers the implications for policy-making in the fields of open space and transformative landscape policy.

Authors

Gerd Lintz Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Mariam Diagayété Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: D2
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

D2 – Ecological glimpses. Or how architectural education encompasses environmental matters

Ecology expresses certain degrees of ambiguity when it is part of the framework of a learning experience. Hypotheses can be almost true or slightly false, as Timothy Morton points out, and we will find ourselves faced with uncountable entities and collective behaviors. It is common for some teachers to share methods with colleagues from other fields of knowledge when we organize a new semester. Furthermore, we have a new profile of students, with little interest for common issues and anchored in the virtual, as Michelle Serres alerts us. In this context, our design practices work from hypotheses that become valid as the course progresses, and that end up giving shape to new epistemologies that will be received with suspicion by other colleagues, depending on how often the descriptors of academic structures are renewed.

How do architecture schools such as Alicante in the peripheral and south Europe operate in this context? First, with synergies among the teaching staff, each one with freedom and neighbouring agreements, such as those nests and singing places that Vincianne Despret refers to in her book "Living as birds". Second, with ways to externalize the classrooms in order to make those undergraduate come out of the cave. Third, producing materialities, tangible and liveable, for example, instruments that dye the river using red cabbage extract (a natural indicator of the pH of liquids), or new custodian entities for a minor sea that has recently acquired legal personality (Mar Menor, Murcia). Fourth, creating spaces for demonstration, experience and enjoyment. Fifth, imagining how to dioramize the stories contained in the students' designs (see <https://floodlands.orsieg.es>). Sixth, with language structures that name and illustrate the variability displayed. This paper unfolds the key-concepts and methods to arrive to these eco-based architectures.

Authors

Jose Carrasco University of Alicante

Antonio Abellán

Parallel Session: D2
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

D2 – Trajectories of mining ecosystems in the perspective of human-environment interrelations.

As mine closures continue, it is imperative to implement a strategic policy that prioritizes the restructuring and restoration of entire post-mining regions rather than just rehabilitating individual mining sites. This shift in approach requires a comprehensive understanding of post-mining areas' evolution and consideration of different potential restoration modes. It is also crucial to assess the cumulative environmental and socioeconomic impacts of the adopted restoration scenarios. Taking these measures can confidently pave the way for a more sustainable and resilient future for post-mining regions.

The work aims to define conceptually trajectories of the mining ecosystem depending on the mode of reclamation and the role of natural, human, social, and built capital in the individual stages of transformation. Using cases from the Konin Mining District in the Eastern Greater Poland region, we analyzed the circumstances of the trajectories of mining ecosystems restored towards agriculture, forest, water, and other (economic and recreational) directions in the context of different forms of capital that expressed the assets, constraints and needs of the mining region. The investigation has proven that for effective restoration, the essential condition is to recognize the role of individual elements of the social and ecological system in connection with subsequent phases of the transformation of mining ecosystems. Another finding is the appreciation of the role of ecosystem services as a valuable tool for comparing the benefits for humans resulting from the functioning of ecosystems in different phases of transformation. Ecosystem services, as a concept linking people and natural ecosystems, can be incorporated into the design, practice and evaluation of restoration projects to promote restoration's socioeconomic and ecological benefits. The approach creates a space for collaboration between stakeholders (mine operators, local authorities, residents) for agreed, reasonable region restoration decisions.

Authors

Katarzyna Fagiewicz Adam Mickiewicz University

Andrzej Mizgajski Calisia University Kalisz

Parallel Session: D3
Format: Presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

D3 – Indikatoren zu Ökosystemen und ihren Leistungen für Deutschland im neuen IÖR-Forschungsdatenzentrum

Forschungsdaten machen einen großen Anteil des menschlichen Wissensbestandes aus, deren freier Zugang zu den Grundpfeilern einer demokratischen Gesellschaft gehört. Das Leibniz-Institut für ökologische Raumentwicklung Dresden entwickelt ein Forschungsdatenzentrum (FDZ) besonderer Art, denn dieses Angebot umfasst hochaufgelöste objekt- und raumbezogene Daten und richtet sich an Akteure in Forschung, Politik, Verwaltung, NGOs und die an nachhaltiger Entwicklung interessierte Öffentlichkeit. Innerhalb des FDZ werden Informationen über die Ökosysteme Deutschlands bereitgestellt. Darin stehen Indikatoren über die Ausdehnung, Zustände und Leistungen der Ökosysteme frei als „Open Data“ für die Öffentlichkeit zur Verfügung.

Auf der Grundlage regelmäßiger Analysen landschaftsbezogener Daten werden Indikatoren für biologische Vielfalt, Ökosystemleistungen sowie Lebensqualität und Umweltgerechtigkeit errechnet, bewertet und bereitgestellt. In diesem Beitrag zeigen wir Daten zur Biodiversität, zum Klimaschutz durch Ökosysteme, zur Klimaanpassung der Städte und zu den Leistungen der urbanen grünen Infrastruktur. Diese Ergebnisse dienen als Grundlage für gesellschaftliche Debatten um Strategien zum Schutz von Landschaften und Biodiversität. Seit dem Beginn des Jahres 2023 werden im FDZ schrittweise Daten aus früheren Projekten ins Netz überführt; in den kommenden Jahren werden diese ergänzt um neu entwickelte Indikatoren, die bestehende Lücken ausfüllen können. Datenbestände aus der Forschung werden so für die deutsche und internationale Öffentlichkeit erschlossen und zukunftsicher nutzbar gemacht.

Authors

Ralf-Uwe Syrbe Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Sophie Meier Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Claudia Dworczyk Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Karsten Grunewald Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: D3
Format: Presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

D3 – Different policies and different urban form? Policy impacts on the urban form in the French-German border-region

Urban form is key in shaping sustainable cities. Consequently, sustainability strategies focus on concepts such as compactness and no-net-land-take. These strategies translate into land policies and concrete decision making on-site that promote density or efficient building types. While countries like France and Germany have committed to and established the similar goals in their respective sustainability strategies, their implemented policies vary largely due to different land policy systems. Thus, we hypothesise that their respective impact on urban form will differ, too. However, an understanding of the precise impacts of different land policies on urban form remains vague. Therefore, this contribution addresses the question “How do patterns of urban form differ on the background of different land policy systems?”. A comparative approach is proposed to analyse the complexity of urban form across land policy systems. For this, the French-German border region serves as a test ground to compare the patterns of urban form emerging within the context of the two sustainability pathways. The study relies on a data-driven approach containing building footprint, parcel, and street network information deriving from harmonised national data sources. Residential development projects are identified by construction time (1990–2020) at the building block level and are assessed by their urban form characteristics. These are achieved by applying landscape metrics, supervised classification of building types, and regional accessibility calculation. The resulting patterns of urban form are compared and discussed against the backdrop of the two countries’ policy pathways. While different patterns arise, such as more homogenous large-scale developments in France and a lower density variance in Germany, the differences along the analysed time line are more complex. The results allow for a deeper understand of the relation between urban form and land policies. They allow stakeholders to address the issues of sustainable urban form more effectively in policy making.

Authors

Mathias Jehling Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Caspar Kleiner Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Bénédicte Bucher French National Institute for Geographical and Forest Information (IGN)

Thomas Hartmann Technical University of Dortmund

Parallel Session: D3
Format: Presentation
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

D3 – Understand the evolving human-river relationships with social science methods.

Rivers are social-ecological systems, but in urban environments, they often degrade into mere conduits, lacking the vitality to offer nature experiences. In response, river restoration, fueled by Nature-based Solutions, has been increasingly adopted worldwide to enhance the ecological quality of river-floodplain systems and rekindle the human-nature bond. However, in river studies, the social dimension often remains underrepresented, overshadowed by the predominant focus on hydrology and ecology in these projects. To address this gap, our research explores the evolving relationship between rivers and society, employing social science methodologies and case studies in France, Mainland China, and Hong Kong (HK). From 2020 to 2022, we conducted three public surveys in Tours (France), Chongqing, Wuhan, and Hangzhou (Mainland China), and HK to understand societal perceptions, interactions with rivers, preferences for river restoration, and public willingness to engage in river management. Our findings indicate that restored river sites foster various recreational activities for urban citizens. They also reveal an emotional connection to rivers, influenced by cultural contexts, such as the 'mother river' concept in China. Significantly, we noted that childhood river experiences impact individuals' current attitudes toward river environments. Leveraging these findings, we've initiated a global survey in partnership with the UNESCO-IHP Global Network of Water Museums. Available in seven languages, the survey aims to compare human-river relationships across various sociocultural contexts. It's being circulated in Water Museums throughout Asia, Europe, and the Americas. These studies represent a crucial step in incorporating social perspectives into our holistic understanding of rivers as social-ecological systems.

Authors

Yixin Cao University of Lyon

Parallel Session: D4
Format: Dialogue session
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

D4 – Leveraging transformative change for biodiversity in spatial planning: Science meets practice

Global biodiversity is being degraded at unprecedented rates, impacting not only the nature but also human health and long-term economic growth. Rapid urbanization and land use change are among the main drivers of biodiversity loss. Various instruments have been developed to prevent biodiversity loss in spatial planning processes, however, the integration of biodiversity into spatial development is not satisfying.

Open questions include: How can (urban) biodiversity and ecosystem services become part of a broader understanding of the civic (built) culture through spatial development? What are the gaps identified in practice with regards to leveraging transformative change for biodiversity in spatial planning, in particular, concerning transformative visions and instruments (e.g., spatial planning instruments, environmental assessment instruments, economic and financial instruments)? What are promising ideas to be matured in future research and policy making? Against this background, the interactive session would like to discuss how planning can enhance biodiversity and contribute to transformation.

The session will be held in English and German to welcome practitioners and researchers from all disciplines and regions. It will start with a short introductory input from the BioValue project¹ (10 min in English with slides in German), followed by group discussions (5 min for instructions and redirecting participants to different tables, and 25 min for discussions).

Participants can choose tables on 3 topics:

- 1) What instruments work in practice to enhance biodiversity in spatial planning?
- 2) How could we broaden the spatial planning Tool-kit for enhancing biodiversity?
- 3) How can spatial planning contribute to transformation?

Tables will be available for both English and German speakers. The number of tables will be flexible to accommodate group size and language preferences of the participants. After the group discussion, each table will report to the plenary with 3-5 most promising results, followed by plenary discussion (20 min).

¹ BioValue is a Horizon Europe project that explores how spatial planning can leverage transformative change for biodiversity.

Authors

Yuanzao Zhu Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung – UFZ

Karla E. Locher-Krause Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung – UFZ

Heidi Wittmer Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung – UFZ

Parallel Session: D5
Format: Presentation
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

D5 – Conflicts as indicators of socio-ecological injustices in urban energy transitions

A shift towards renewable energy is essential to attain national, regional, and local low-carbon objectives. Cities, being significant energy consumers, play a crucial role in this transition. While many cities worldwide are ambitiously pursuing 100% renewable energy targets, conflicts related to large-scale urban renewable energy projects have surfaced. These conflicts often arise from the spatial dimension of urban energy transitions, involving energy production infrastructure within or near city boundaries. Particularly complex situations arise when renewable energy projects are proposed on greenfield sites with high ecological value, creating a clash between decarbonization goals and the impact on urban landscapes and biodiversity. This opposition, known as the 'green-on-green' conflict, exposes fault lines within climate action and nature conservation in cities. Two cases of green-on-green conflicts, involving large-scale urban solar farms in Edmonton, Canada, and Leipzig, Germany, illustrate this dilemma. I argue that while these projects contribute to climate goals, siting them on ecologically valuable greenfield sites compromises the city's commitment to addressing the ecological and biodiversity crisis. I propose a socio-ecological justice framework for planners to navigate tensions and trade-offs arising from green-on-green conflicts. Urban energy transitions focused solely on carbon reduction perpetuate existing unsustainability and injustices in cities.

Authors

Neelakshi Joshi Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: D5
Format: Presentation
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

D5 – How can effectiveness be balanced with cost in biodiversity conservation? Cross-scale ecological network planning in the Yangtze River Delta, China

The Yangtze River Delta has suffered significant habitat fragmentation and biodiversity loss due to urban expansion, functional zoning, and land consolidation over the past 30 years. Despite its designation as a national demonstration zone for ecological development in 2019, existing ecological conservation and permanent basic farmland redlines set by territorial planning have failed to protect key habitats for local species. Planned corridors have primarily focused on cultural protection, tourism, and flood control rather than habitat connectivity. An urgent need exists for an ecological network (EN) of high-value habitats and corridors, yet current EN planning faces challenges in achieving both cost-effectiveness and cross-scale coordination. In this study, we explored a cross-scale EN planning approach within the demonstration zone, hypothesizing that habitat preferences and dispersal abilities could serve as criteria for selecting multiple species, thereby balancing conservation effectiveness with construction costs. We categorized 17 bird and eight mammal species into 12 scenarios based on their habitat preferences and dispersal capacities for EN construction and evaluation. Our hypothesis was supported by evidence showing that the EN designed for species with broad habitat preferences (forests, croplands, water bodies, wetlands, etc.) and high dispersal capacity (10–15 km) achieved the highest conservation effectiveness at the lowest cost. This approach was further validated in a pilot new town project, revealing that the minimum patch size for identifying high-quality habitats and the maximum dispersal distance for defining corridor lengths must be adjusted based on species characteristics as the scale shifts. Additionally, we proposed strategies to integrate these ENs with existing territorial planning and to restore ecological continuity where corridors intersect roads and planned scenic and blue-green corridors. This cost-effective approach provides new insights for targeting focal species in multi-species EN planning and provides scientific support for delineating protected areas and ecological corridors within territorial planning frameworks.

Authors

Yuting Xie Institute of Landscape Architecture, Zhejiang University

Qichen Hong Institute of Landscape Architecture, Zhejiang University

Qie Shi Institute of Landscape Architecture, Zhejiang University / Center for Balance Architecture, Zhejiang University

Xia Sheng Institute of Landscape Architecture, Zhejiang University / Center for Balance Architecture, Zhejiang University

Parallel Session: D5
Format: Presentation
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

D5 – New Insights into intercity ecological synergy: revealing community structures and their drivers through the dynamics of ecosystem service flows

Due to the general dynamics and externalities associated with ecosystem biophysical processes, cross-regional synergistic governance has emerged as a pivotal approach for sustainable ecological management. Cross-regional governance inevitably involves multiple actors with different geographical characteristics, especially various cities. Therefore, the effectiveness of such governance relies not only on the overall synergy level within the city network but also on tailored governance strategies that accommodate the unique ecological linkage characteristics of each locale within the network. However, most previous research has characterized inter-city ecological linkages by static indicators such as geographic distance, ignoring the spatial dynamics of ecological flows.

Based on the spatial mechanism of ecosystem service flow (ESF), this research took ESF as an indicator to characterize ecological linkages, focusing on two types of ecosystem services—directional flow (water conservation) and omnidirectional flow (carbon sequestration)—to explore how to quantitatively identify and spatially visualize the inter-city ecological relationship networks, and precisely formulate efficient cross-regional ecological governance strategies based on these networks.

Specifically, this research uses the Yangtze River Delta region as a case study, constructing ecological adjacency matrices for 40 cities within the region based on two types of ESF. Then, we deconstructed the overall network structure and local community types of the two inter-city ecological relationship networks based on the ecological adjacency matrix by using complex network and community detection methods. Finally, leveraging the general nesting spatial model, we analyzed and compared the key drivers of these ecological relationship networks at both city and community levels, thereby formulating an integrated cross-regional ecological governance strategy that encompasses both types of ecological linkages. This research framework brings ESF into the city network study, which provides significant foundational support for cross-regional ecological synergistic governance decision-making.

Authors

Wentao Yan Tongji University / Anhui Jianzhu University

Yuting Huang Tongji University

Zhechen Zhou East China University of Science and Technology

Yarong Cao South China University of Technology

Abstracts

Parallel Sessions E

Parallel Session: E1
Format: Short Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

E1 – Nature's diverse values in urban planning: uncovering conflicting and shared views from the inner worlds of planners

The coexistence of life on planet Earth is threatened. Especially, cities are driving the severe sustainability crises, such as species extinction and climate change. These crises in the outside world are well researched, but less attention seems to be paid to people's inner world: A deep-rooted crisis in our relationship with nature, with paradigms, world views and values based on domination and exploitation, silencing the voice of more-than-human nature. Despite the growing interest in nature-based solutions in cities, urban planning seems to be based primarily on anthropocentric and utilitarian ethics. In this context, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) emphasises the recognition of pluricentric perspectives and multiple values of nature. Their meaningful inclusion into decision-making is seen as a leverage point towards just and sustainable futures.

In our empirical contribution, we analyse the diverse values of nature to better recognise intrinsic and relational values that go beyond instrumental relationships in urban planning. The subjective (i.e. first-person) experiences of planners will be elicited to enable a deeper understanding of their inner worlds. We address the following research questions: What personal views on nature's diverse values are held by municipal actors in urban planning? Which conflicting and shared views on nature's values strengthen or hinder urban sustainability transformations?

We use the Q-methodology, a mixed methods approach that combines qualitative data collection with a subsequent quantitative correlation and factor analysis. This involves conducting 25 interviews with employees from different departments of the Dresden city administration to capture the individually perceived importance of nature through the lens of three value dimensions (intrinsic, relational and instrumental). At the IOER-conference, we present the results of our research. In a second step, we reflect on the conclusions that can be drawn for research and policy in relation to urban sustainability transformation and nature.

Authors

Philip Harms Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: E1
Format: Short Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

E1 – Piloting the fosterage of urban residents’ resonances with nature through a 5-week-long ritual: Learnings, limits and lookout for sustainability transformations

The Earth’s limits are transgressed, yet reactions to that are diverse. While the climate crisis causes increasingly affective disorders such as climate anxiety or massive rage, many individuals appear to remain mute towards nature and the need to live more sustainably (Artmann 2023). Aiming to foster more individuals’ resonances with the social-ecological crisis, science pleads to holistically connect people with nature – also their own inner nature including body and emotions – in order to respect nonhuman and human nature’s needs and limits (Müller et al. 2023). Yet, mindsets of a human-nature separation and the increasing urbanization that diminishes human-nature experiences are argued to be hampering factors. Hence, Ives et al. (2018) stress the importance of intervening notably in cities. In this regard, affect-laden experiential interventions and rituals appear to play a pivotal role in overcoming mute human-nature relationships. Beside the experiential aspect, it is stressed to inform the interventions with relational ideas and capabilities so that individuals might be supported to cope with existing emotions (Bogner et al. 2024) and intrapersonal obstacles (Varutti 2023).

Against this background, in the feasibility study under consideration, we aimed to foster individual human-nature resonances through a 5-week-long ritual in an urban setting. Hereby, with the help of an app, the participants followed specific sequences of which certain aspects are considered essential for human-nature resonance such as state of openness, acknowledging nature’s Unverfügbarkeit (Rosa 2019), the capabilities of being affected and to respond as well a transformation towards respecting nature’s needs as part of a good life. Our feasibility study combines a quantitative panel-study based on psychological experimental study design including a control group with relational theories. Due to its pilot character, the results don't deliver statistical evidences, yet first gentle confirmations of the intervention in terms of effectiveness for sustainability transformation are visible.

Authors

Susanne Müller Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: E1
Format: Short Presentation
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

E1 – Using Human Scale Development Approach for Transformative Visions in Spatial Development

Global biodiversity assessments identify transformative change as a requirement to reverse the continuing loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services. This entails meeting human needs in significantly less resource-intensive ways and addressing the growing socio-economic inequalities. However, it is difficult for most people to envision desirable lifestyles that are less resource dependent. Spatial planning is central to addressing these challenges. It could support developing visions of desirable futures and outline pathways to significantly reduce the intensity of resource use as well as socio-economic inequalities.

We explore the potential of combining the Wittmer et al.'s (2021) transformative change framework with the Human Scale Development approach introduced by Max-Neef et al. (1991) to enable planners to try out bolder approaches to spatial development. The framework offers building blocks to support operationalizing transformative change. We use three ambitions adapted for spatial planning in the BioValue project¹ to integrate sustainability conditions and to articulate biodiversity within positive visions. For visioning, the Human Scale Development approach provides an entry point to envision strategies that fulfil human needs in sustainability settings. It allows spatial planners to become aware of desired conditions of a good life based on the satisfaction of human needs, and enhances the accessibility and operationalization of sustainable development. By discussing positive visions at individual and collective levels, the approach encourages inner shifts and changes in understanding and respecting the balanced relationship between humans and nature. We present an experimental use of this approach in sustainability transformation contexts and discuss challenges and opportunities.

¹ BioValue is a Horizon Europe project that explores how spatial planning can leverage transformative change for biodiversity.

Authors

Yuanzao Zhu Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung – UFZ

Heidi Wittmer Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung – UFZ

Parallel Session: E2
Format: Dialogue Session
Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

E2 – An Art-Based Research Workshop on Envisioning Co-Existence of Wolves and People in Fragmented Landscapes.

For over 150 years, wolves have been almost absent in Central Europe. In the past decade, however, their populations are on the rise again. During the absence of wolves, the Central European landscape has been significantly changed. A variety of drivers, including increased income and a value system that prioritizes certain forms of a good living —particularly those characterized by the construction of detached single-family homes and car-bound mobility infrastructure—have led to widespread urban sprawl across Europe. Consequently, wolves' habitats today are often fragmented by human settlements, leading to increased crossovers between wolves and the everyday lives of people.

Current approaches to understanding the relationship between wolf recolonization and human needs rarely incorporate positive visions of a future where both wolves and people can flourish. Wolves have long been associated with negative notions in human societies. This workshop aims to integrate knowledge towards envisioning a future where wolves and people coexist. To this end, we draw on the intersubjective knowledge of each workshop participant in a creative and pleasurable way. Everyone is welcome to join and no prior knowledge on the subject is required.

We start with a short introduction of the topic by the moderators. Then we use an associative card game in a small group setting to tap on creative thinking and uncover epistemic differences. We do not strive for consensus but attempt to appreciate diverse ideas and balance them against one another. Based on the discussions, in the next step, we translate the individual visions into a shared vision by co-creating an art poster. We end our workshop with a short presentation of each of the posters and a reflection round.

Workshops will be conducted in English, with the option for small group discussions in German provided it is agreeable to all members of the group. Credits for the workshop's foundational principles are attributed to Alina Kaltenberg and Astrid Gläsel. Maximum number of workshop participants 20.

Authors

Anna-Katharina Brenner Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Wenjing Xu Senckenberg Biodiversity / Climate Research Centre

Parallel Session: E3
Format: Short Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

E3 – A Digital Tool for Green Infrastructure Planning in Metropolitan Rural Areas for Multi-Scenario Needs

The advancement of rural revitalization is influencing the current ecological spatial development process in Chinese metropolitan rural areas. In the context of Shanghai's urban-rural coordinated development, there is a targeted focus on planning green infrastructure for different typical rural areas in the near and distant suburbs.

Due to the lack of quantitative assessment of ecological benefits and fragmented information data across governing units, the workflow of rural ecological spatial planning is hindered. Building upon the dimensions of ecosystem service provisioning, regulating, and supporting, attempts are made to achieve a balance of green infrastructure supply trade-offs across various scenarios using digital planning tools, and a workflow of ecological spatial governance centered around rural green infrastructure (RGI) planning is proposed. In the peri-urban industrial-type Beiguan village, comprehensive evaluation, governance, and data tracking of rural land requisition processes are realized, enabling a multi-scale examination of land transformation demands and impacts, and facilitating the updating of land transformation assessment systems through refined ecological spatial governance. While in the ecologically-oriented village of Shuiku located in the distant outskirts, a multi-factor ecological data quantification toolkit has been developed to realize the valorization of ecological benefits. Additionally, the workflow of ecological spatial management and maintenance has been integrated, building a multifaceted collaborative network among stakeholders. Ultimately, through co-evaluation of ecological value and construction needs, a systematic innovation of the decision-making logic in ecological planning is achieved, thereby enhancing overall effectiveness.

Through the summary of different scenarios practices of rural green infrastructure planning in Shanghai, it is proposed to incorporate ecological values into the decision-making system, supporting precise positioning of rural green infrastructure according to local conditions, and providing suggestions for optimizing the workflow of comprehensive ecological governance and standardizing future ecological governance data.

Authors

Nannan Dong Tongji University

Mingqi Zhao Tongji University

Weixuan Wei Tongji University

Parallel Session: E3
Format: Short presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

E3 – Atmosphären und leibliche Kommunikation als Dimensionen lebenswerter und nachhaltiger Wohngebiete

Die bauliche Struktur und die sozio-demografischen sowie sozio-ökonomischen Bedingungen der Großwohnsiedlungen in Ostdeutschland spiegeln vielfältige städtebauliche und gesellschaftliche Realitäten sowie Reaktionen auf sich schnell wandelnde Rahmenbedingungen wider. Gerade in diesen Nachbarschaften sind öffentliche Räume von großer Bedeutung. Doch was ist, wenn die baulichen und sozialräumlichen Voraussetzungen eigentlich erwünschtes Miteinander, positive Raumeignungen und somit das Entstehen lebenswerter Orte behindern?

Anhand von Befunden zu öffentlichen Räumen in drei ostdeutschen Großwohnsiedlungen werden Potenziale und Defizite dieser Räume zur Entwicklung lebenswerter und nachhaltiger Wohngebiete diskutiert (Friedrich, Rößler 2023a). Ergänzend zu baulichen und infrastrukturellen Defiziten gibt es teils unsichtbare Konflikte in öffentlichen Räumen, die das Zusammenleben, Wohlfühlen und somit das Entfalten eines Zuhauses erschweren (Friedrich, Rößler 2023b).

Mit Hilfe der Neuen Phänomenologie insbesondere der leiblichen Kommunikation und Atmosphären (Schmitz, 1967) beschreiben wir gelebte Situationen (Rothacker, 1982) aus der Perspektive verschiedener Zielgruppen. Dabei spielen Gefühle, die zwischen inneren und äußeren Stimmungen eines Menschen changieren, aber auch einladende oder unbehagliche sogar ängstigende Einflüsse eine Rolle.

Auf der Grundlage von Atmosphären aus phänomenologischer Perspektive betrachten wir Leiblichkeit in städtischen Räumen. Dem Ansatz der Neuen Phänomenologie, Gefühle nicht nur als rein subjektives Innenleben zu verstehen folgend, machen wir die Chancen leiblicher Kommunikation für soziale Kontakte sichtbar.

An Hand konkreter Beispiele zeigen wir auf, warum Menschen Orte beispielsweise als angenehm oder unangenehm deuten. Prägend sind hierbei: Möglichkeiten der Begegnung und der (gemeinschaftlichen) Raumeignung (z. B. Gärtnern), aber auch Erfahrungen von Abwertung (z. B. Rassismus) oder negative Raumeignung Dritter (z. B. Drogenkonsum).

Das Wissen um die menschlichen Verstrickungen mit gefühlten und gebauten Räumen bietet eine wichtige Grundlage für passende bauliche und soziale Interventionen im öffentlichen Raum als Voraussetzung für die Entwicklung lebenswerter und nachhaltiger Wohngebiete.

Literatur

Rothacker, Erich (1982): Philosophische Anthropologie, 5. Aufl. Bonn.

Schmitz, Hermann (1964-1969): System der Philosophie, Bonn.

Authors

Katja Friedrich Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development / IZS

Stefanie Rößler Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development / IZS

Parallel Session: E3
Format: Presentation
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

E3 – A new beginning for Strasbourg's green belt

Strasbourg's green belt was created 100 years ago following the destruction of the city's last rampart belt. Surrounded by non-buildable land, the green belt constituted an undeveloped area of over 1,400 hectares between the city center and the suburbs.

To prevent anarchic urbanization and land speculation, the municipal authorities decided to prevent private construction on the site. The aim was to create a series of parks and new districts. A major international competition was organized in 1925. However, the Second World War brought the project to a halt. Despite a few communal and allotment gardens and small green spaces, from the 1960s onwards the area was mainly used to build several freeways and large public facilities.

The result is a vast, highly fragmented and mineralized area. Residual spaces are numerous and of low quality. It acts as a bulwark between the heart of Strasbourg and the suburbs, much like the expressway ring road around Paris. Pollution is high. No fewer than 300,000 cars travel along it every day.

New parameters are leading us to reconsider the place of the green belt in the city. These include the objectives of combating heat islands, reducing traffic and halting the artificialization of land by 2050. With the election of a new, ecologically-minded municipality, Strasbourg is putting its urban planners to work to initiate a process of renaturation of the area. To achieve this titanic task, which will probably take more than 15 years, the municipal authorities are relying on various projects. The construction of a new tramway to the north of the conurbation and the redevelopment of the area around the soccer stadium are intended to kick-start change. But can this piecemeal approach really change things?

Authors

Tristan Siebert Ecole nationale supérieure d'architecture de Strasbourg

Hélène Antoni Ecole nationale supérieure d'architecture de Strasbourg

Parallel Session: E5
Format: Short presentation
Track: 6. Open Topic

E5 – An IPBES-like assessment for Germany’s urban areas: Insights from the project “Faktencheck Artenvielfalt”

In the face of global ecological degradation, several biodiversity assessments have been carried out under different initiatives and at different scales to synthesise knowledge on different aspects of biodiversity change. In recent years, the most prominent effort has been that of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), which has by now conducted several assessments at global and continental scales. Mirroring the efforts of IPBES, the project “Faktencheck Artenvielfalt” was launched, funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research as part of the Research Initiative for the Conservation of Biodiversity. The aim of the project was to conduct an assessment for Germany, synthesising knowledge on biodiversity status and trends, direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity change, consequences of biodiversity change in terms of ecosystem services, actions taken to protect biodiversity, and transformation potentials for different habitat types, including urban areas. In this presentation we will share insights from the assessment's chapter on urban areas, focusing on indirect and direct drivers of biodiversity change, relationships between biodiversity and ecosystem services, as well as visions for the future of human-nature relations (following IPBES’s Nature Futures Framework and the Multiple Values of Nature Framework), in line with the conference's overall theme “Space & Transformation: Living in Harmony with Nature”. As this kind of assessment provides a snapshot of the existing knowledge landscape, our talk aims at facilitating a joint discussion with session participants on topics such as existing knowledge gaps and corresponding research priorities for the future to support the (land and social-ecological) transformations needed to live in harmony with nature.

Authors

André Mascarenhas University of Stuttgart

Dagmar Haase Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

Josef Kaiser Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

Thilo Wellmann Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

Parallel Session: E5
Format: Presentation
Track: 6. Open topic

E5 – Perspectives of landscape criticality

Connectivity and fragmentation represent common antagonists in landscape ecology. Percolation theory predicts an abrupt phase transition between connected and fragmented states, or vice versa. We systematically explore the percolation-like transition of urban built-up areas. Specifically, we explore spatial clustering according to which any two locations belong to the same cluster if their distance is smaller than a predefined threshold. Changing this threshold, we identify the critical value at which a system-spanning cluster emerges. For the first time, we perform a global analysis and provide critical distances for sub-national units, tiles, and moving windows. To conclude we speculate about ecological implications and the mobility of land-animals.

Authors

Diego Rybski Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development / Complexity Science Hub Vienna

Anna-Katharina Brenner Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Tobias Krüger Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Martin Schorcht Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Md Imtiaz Uddin Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Martin Behnisch Leibniz-Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Parallel Session: E5
Format: Presentation
Track: 6. Open topic

E5 – A conceptual framework to study transformative change and innovation in non-core regions and steps towards operationalisation

This paper aims to contribute to the study of socio-ecological transformations in space, and particularly focuses on the development of transformative capacity and innovation in non-core regions.

Debates on the role of space in transitions span the overlapping research fields of Regional Studies and Sustainability Transitions (Hansen and Coenen, 2015; Baatz et al. 2024) as well as Urban Transitions Research (Wolfram, Borgström and Farrelly, 2019; Hölscher and Frantzeskaki, 2021). Within these debates, the ability of social spaces to deliberately create and establish fundamentally new ways of operating that address the principal causes of sustainability crisis has been termed “Transformative Capacity” (TC) (Wolfram, 2016; Ziervogel, Cowen and Ziniades, 2016; Mehryar et al. 2022). As part of research on urban change, the TC framework has been developed as an analytical tool mainly for metropolitan areas (Wolfram et al. 2019; Tuominen et al., 2022), but it is also relevant in more peripheral regions (Witzell et al., 2022).

The contribution of this paper is twofold. First, we enrich the concept of Transformative Capacity by connecting it to several research fields that have a traditionally strong spatial focus and have recently fostered discussion on transformative change. These include the research on Regional Innovation Systems in Economic Geography (Tödtling et al. 2022), research on rural Social Enterprises (Martens et al. 2021), and sociological insights into regional innovation dynamics (John and Boos, 2021). The key complementarity that allows conceptual connection between these perspectives is offered by their common focus on innovation directed at social or transformative change.

Second, by building on relational approaches to core and non-core regions (Bathelt and Glückler, 2011; Hansen and Coenen, 2015), we highlight the challenges and potentials for Transformative Capacity development in peripheral regions. Ultimately, we derive conclusions for the empirical application of this framework in these spatial contexts.

Authors

Sabine Marr Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Artem Korzhenevych Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Abstracts

Poster Party

Format: Poster party

Track: 1. Positive visions of a good life that inspire and motivate individual and collective actors in spatial development

Inspiring Positive Visions of a Sustainable Future with Solar Cookers

In a world where the preservation of ecosystems and biodiversity is paramount, solar cookers emerge as a beacon of hope for sustainable development. This poster explores the role of solar cookers in shaping positive visions of a good life, inspiring individuals and communities to adopt environmentally friendly cooking practices. By harnessing the power of the sun to prepare meals, solar cookers not only reduce carbon emissions but also enhance self-reliance and resilience in the face of environmental challenges. Through case studies and practical examples, this poster highlights the transformative impact of integrating solar cookers into spatial development strategies, paving the way for a greener and more harmonious future.

Authors

Magaly Ines Beltran Siñani ALLCOT S.A.

Format: Poster party
Track: 2. Strategies and tools for transformative governance, planning, innovation and revitalisation

KlimaOasen – A participatory process to develop nature-based solutions on the University of Stuttgart’s campuses

As institutions that promote learning and innovation with a responsibility towards society, universities can play an important role in advancing the development of nature-based solutions (NBS), including leading by example. In this context, university campuses become important locations to implement NBS, but to succeed in that task one needs to understand and navigate the complex governance structures of a university. Nevertheless, guidelines and scientific literature pertaining to NBS development focused on university campuses are still limited. In this contribution, we present insights from the project KlimaOasen (Climate Oases), funded by Stuttgart’s Klima-Innovationsfonds and carried out jointly by the Institute of Landscape Planning and Ecology and the Green Office of the University of Stuttgart, Germany. The project’s ultimate goal was to promote NBS on campus for climate adaptation, focusing on the evaluation of organizational structures and potential implementation enablers or barriers, and to connect this with the current discourse on campus climate adaptation. To achieve that, we designed and conducted a participatory process bringing different actors together, who (would like to) play a role in initiating, implementing, and maintaining NBS at the University of Stuttgart. The process took place mainly through a series of three participatory workshops, involving thirty participants in total. Each workshop had specific objectives, including getting to know different initiatives and actors, gathering initial ideas for NBS development, discussing and assessing concrete potential NBS, as well as identifying critical aspects and actors for the planning, implementation and stewardship of NBS. We pursued synergies with teaching activities, whereby students developed concrete NBS proposals for different sites on campus, which were discussed with stakeholders in one of the workshops. The project sparked and facilitated the development of a NBS-roundtable at the University of Stuttgart. Based on the results of the workshops, we synthesized concise recommendations for NBS development on campus.

Authors

André Mascarenhas University of Stuttgart

Kristen Jakstis University of Stuttgart

Leonie Fischer University of Stuttgart

Brigitte-Maria Lorenz University of Stuttgart

Format: Poster party
Track: 3. Complex spatial analyses, indicators, models and simulations

Investigating the Effects of Green Walls on Local Climate Regulation: A Case Study for Dresden

The study strives to explore the potential of facade greening to address urban climate issues and the heat island effect in a part of the city of Dresden, which, due to its specific land cover characteristics, has limited capacity for enhancing greenery. For this aim, this study employs ENVI-met software to simulate the microclimate of the study site, followed by statistical analysis of the outcomes under three scenarios: 'With No Greenery,' "With Trees," and "With Trees & Green Facade."

Therefore, the main question is: What are the regulatory impacts of green facades on thermal comfort parameters within the microclimate of the case study location?

To answer the question, there are sub-questions as follows:

1. What are the specific changes in the microclimate variables (e.g., temperature, mean radiant temperature, humidity, wind speed) attributable to implementing green facades in urban street canyons?
2. What are the specific changes in the microclimate variables (e.g., temperature, mean radiant temperature, humidity, wind speed) attributable to implementing green facades in combination with Trees?
3. What is the effect of implementing green facades on indoor air temperature?

Authors

Amir Raoufi TU-Dresden / IHI / Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

Format: Poster party
Track: 4. Circularity and resilience in building and settlement development

Transformation Pathways towards a Regenerative Built Environment

A significant source of carbon emissions will continue to stem from global building stocks, which are expected to double by 2050. Therefore, cities, understood as socio-ecological nodes, are a central lever to addressing the climate crisis. In this context, we need to move past 'sustainability' towards 'regenerative development', which integrates the internal and external dimensions of the socio-ecological system with the aim to unlearn extractive tendencies and re-connect human activity with the Earth's natural systems.

We showcase the idea of a regenerative built environment for two different contexts reflecting the particular conditions of two urban areas and their associated bioregions in the Global South and North: Thimphu-Paro, Bhutan and Berlin-Brandenburg, Germany.

Embedded in a transformation-lab approach, the starting point was an evidence-based systems analysis, which crosses multiple spatial scales and includes an assessment of the natural resources, the construction sector, the socio-spatial conditions, as well as the mapping of relevant actors, policies, and the innovation landscape.

We explore the facets of regenerative architecture in detail by developing a demonstrator building for each region. Central for both processes is the focus on the material transition in construction by engaging with nature-based supply chains in a holistic way, including its socio-spatial, environmental, and political dimensions.

Throughout the process we employ a participatory approach and explore the communication of results and regional roadmaps through appropriate engagement formats with diverse stakeholders. First results reveal multiple overarching challenges, such as missing markets for reclaimed materials, the novelty of materials and construction techniques being problematic for administrative processes, the acceptance in society, and the extended role of architects. In summary, while first prototypes attract deep interest from different stakeholders including architects, material producers, governmental bodies, and the wider public, there is a long way to go for regenerative practices in construction to become widely implemented.

Authors

Anne Holsten Bauhaus der Erde gGmbH

Format: Poster party
Track: 5. Regeneration of ecosystems and biodiversity as well as nature-based solutions

Compensation planning and implementation for infrastructure projects against the background of increasing drought and water shortage

As part of the impact mitigation regulation under the nature conservation legislation of Germany, Austria and Switzerland (D-A-CH countries), measures are implemented to compensate for unavoidable impairments of nature and landscape resulting from development projects such as highways and railways. Compensation measures are an important instrument for countering global biodiversity decline. However, climate and landscape change pose enormous challenges for the long-term preservation of their functionality. The future-proof orientation of compensation measures is therefore in line with the central European objectives for safeguarding biodiversity in the light of climate change (EU Green Deal, EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030). Heat waves, drought and water scarcity and the associated consequences for groundwater levels and the landscape water balance must be taken into account in compensation planning. Effective implementation of compensation measures includes the following aspects:

1. adaptive management, i.e. adjusting the compensation planning when implementing the areas in order to take account of changing environmental conditions. This can include flexible monitoring and management approaches, to ensure the long-term success of compensation measures. For example, the location of compensation areas and the selection of plants must be rethought.
2. water protection measures, i.e. the integration of measures to mitigate the effects of water scarcity on habitats and species. This could include restoring wetlands and improving water retention in the landscape.

The transnational research project "Compensation areas in transition" presents recommendations for action with regard to how the planning, safeguarding, maintenance and monitoring of compensation areas and measures can be improved in the future.

Authors

Nora Schmidt Hochschule Geisenheim Universtiy

Marianne Darbi Hochschule Geisenheim Universtiy

Format: Poster party
Track: 6. Open topic

A study on Urban-Scale Aerodynamic Roughness Length and Sky View Factor Analysis Using Airborne LiDAR Remote Sensing

In the ongoing urbanization process, the horizontal and vertical expansion of buildings worsens the impacts of the urban heat island (UHI) and weakens the resilience of the urban ecosystem. Planting and growing vertical trees strategically within and around buildings, roads, and parks have proven effective in mitigating these negative effects.

Effective urban planning should not only prioritize organizing urban buildings to improve ventilation for UHI mitigation but also underscore the strategic placement of vertical trees to enhance pedestrian comfort and foster a more resilient urban ecosystem. This study employs airborne LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) remote sensing methodology to identify hotspots with expected weak mean wind environments at the urban scale. Additionally, an analysis of the urban Sky View Factor (SVF) will pinpoint areas requiring vertical tree planting for increased tree canopy to shield against solar radiation.

The study area, spanning 501.5 km² in Incheon Metropolitan City in the northwestern part of South Korea, will be examined using 750 square Lidar data (1.2 km × 1.2 km), classified into ground, building, tree, etc. The computed data will be merged into a comprehensive urban-scale raster dataset, enabling multi-scale surveillance of urban areas. Furthermore, GIS-based data overlay analysis will assist in geographically and demographically explaining urban settings.

The research outcomes will offer practical insights for planning and designing climate-friendly urban settings by prioritizing vulnerable urban districts and supporting spatial information. Through the optimization of both building and tree settings, the study aims to improve urban ventilation and enhance pedestrian well-being, thereby contributing to the overall improvement of urban environments.

Authors

Seungman An Korea Research Institute for Human Settlements

Wolfgang Wende Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Format: Poster party
Track: 6. Open Topic

LSUTDI: A Hybrid Deep Learning Model for Imputing Large-Scale Urban Traffic Data

Large-scale urban traffic monitoring data is fundamental to advancing intelligent transportation systems and is indispensable for enhancing research and application in traffic management and urban planning. However, the reliability of such data is often compromised due to the presence of missing values. Current methodologies, largely focused on general time series imputation using basic statistical or machine learning methods, are primarily validated on freeway data, often neglecting the complexities of urban road networks and resulting in a lack of specialized solutions for urban road data. This leaves a significant research gap in creating more advanced imputation models for filling gaps in missing traffic data. To tackle this, we present the LSUTDI (Large Scale Urban Traffic Data Imputer) model, a hybrid deep learning-based model designed specifically for large urban traffic data imputation. This model leverages the combined strengths of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Networks (Bidirectional RNNs), and Multi-head Attention mechanisms to effectively impute missing data in traffic datasets. We tested the LSUTDI model on the VAMOS dataset, which contains traffic monitoring data from Dresden city. Our results show that not only does the model effectively handle missing data, but it also performs better than many existing state-of-the-art models.

Authors

Jyotirmaya Ijaradar TU Dresden

Format: Poster party

SALUTE4CE Integrated environmental management of small green spaces in urban areas

Authors

Jessica Hemingway Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Juliane Mathey Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Peter Wirth Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Social and innovative Platform On cultural Tourism (SPOT) and its potential towards deepening Europeanisation

Authors

Ralf-Uwe Syrbe Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Jessica Hemingway Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Bianca Eckelmann Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Ina Neumann Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Peter Wirth Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Do the nesting holes suit the bee? Validating expert estimation of wild bee habitat with findings from field studies

Authors

Sophie Meier Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Open space, policy, planning, chance

Authors

Gerd Lintz Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

Mariam Diagayété Leibniz-Institut of Ecological Urban und Regional Development

University Campus Healthscapes: Using the university as an urban lab for designing health-promoting built-environments

Authors

Rana Abdelkader Dresden Leibniz Graduate School

8 Venue floor plan & directions

Information about the venue may also be found on the IOER conference website:
<https://conference.ioer.info/venue>

Deutsches Hygiene Museum Dresden Orientation Plan

The IOER Conference will take place at the Deutsches Hygiene-Museum Dresden (DHMD), located at Lingnerplatz 1, 01069 Dresden.

Image: DHMD / IOER, U. Schinke

Map and directions to the Zentrum für Baukultur (ZfBK) in the Kulturpalast

The Poster Party will take place at the Zentrum für Baukultur (ZfBK) in the Kulturpalast Dresden which is located near the historical city centre of Dresden. It is about a 20-minute walk from the Deutsches Hygiene-Museum Dresden (DHMD).

Image: U. Schinke / IOER Media

9 Acknowledgements

We would like to express a sincere thank you to the following individuals that made this conference possible

Core organisation team

Wolfgang Wende
Jessica Hemingway
Christina Kraatz
Katrin Vogel

Active support

Marc Wolfram
Heike Bernhardt and Elke Mootz

Technical, communications, knowledge, and workshop support (in alphabetical order)

Nicolaas Bongaerts
Alejandro De Castro Mazarro
Sven Haase and Oliver Bordt
Heike Hensel
Carsten Hantzsch
Philip Harms
Mathias Jehling
Henriette John
Neelakshi Joshi
Birgit Kochan and Mario Bieh
Kerstin Ludewig
Sophie Meier
Susanne Müller
Alfred Olfert
Anja Pohl
Anna-Maria Schielicke
Ulrike Schinke
Ralf-Uwe Syrbe
Klaus Uhlich
Sabine Witschas
Suili Xiao

Student Assistants

Sandra Fiedler
Kristina Fjodorowa
Alexander Maximilian Haase
Paul Reier
Negar Tavoosi
Jana Winkler

**Thank you as well to individuals that we did not mention here but that supported,
advertised or contributed in some way to the organisation of this event 😊**